

**Actions to Crimes Against
Rights on the Internet under
The Council of Europe and
The Charter of Human Rights:**

A Case Study on the Applicability of the Budapest Convention

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Chapter 1: Function of the Council of Europe and the Jurisprudence of the Budapest Convention

PART 1. ESTABLISHMENT OF THE COUNCIL

The council

A Council of Europe ("the Council") is hereby established. It shall be a permanent institution and shall have the power to exercise its jurisdiction over its member states for the most serious crimes of humanitarian concern, and shall be complementary to national digital rights violations. The jurisdiction and functioning of the Council shall be governed by the provisions of this Convention.

Relationship of the council with the United Nations

The Council shall be brought into relationship with the United Nations through an agreement to be approved by the Assembly of States Parties to this Convention and thereafter concluded by the President of the Council on its behalf.

Seat of the council

1. The seat of the Council shall be established in Brussels in Belgium ("the host State").
2. The Council shall enter into a headquarters agreement with the host State, to be approved by the Member States and thereafter concluded by the President of the Court on its behalf.
3. The Council may sit elsewhere, whenever it considers it desirable within Europe.

Legal status and power of the court

1. The Council shall have legal personality amongst its 47 state members. It shall also have such legal capacity as may be necessary for the exercise of its functions and the fulfillment of its purposes.
2. The Council may exercise its functions and powers, on the territory of any State Party adhered to the Council.

PART 2. INTERNET RIGHTS AND PRINCIPLES**Universality and Equality**

All humans are born free and equal in dignity and rights, which must be respected, protected and fulfilled in the online environment.

Rights and Social Justice

The Internet is a space for the promotion, protection and fulfilment of human rights and the advancement of social justice. Everyone has the duty to respect the human rights of all others in the online environment

Accessibility

Everyone has an equal right to access and use a secure and open Internet.

Expression and Association

Everyone has the right to seek, receive, and impart information freely on the Internet without censorship or other interference. Everyone also has the right to associate freely through and on the Internet, for social, political, cultural or other purposes

Privacy and Data Protection

Everyone has the right to privacy online. This includes freedom from surveillance, the right to use encryption, and the right to online anonymity. Everyone also has the right to data protection, including control over personal data collection, retention, processing, disposal and disclosure

Life, Liberty and Security

The rights to life, liberty, and security must be respected, protected and fulfilled online. These rights must not be infringed upon, or used to infringe other rights, in the online environment.

Diversity

Cultural and linguistic diversity on the Internet must be promoted, and technical and policy innovation should be encouraged to facilitate plurality of expression.

Network Equality

Everyone shall have universal and open access to the Internet's content, free from discriminatory prioritization, filtering or traffic control on commercial, political or other grounds.

Standards and Regulation

The Internet's architecture, communication systems, and document and data formats shall be based on open standards that ensure complete interoperability, inclusion and equal opportunity for all.

Governance

Human rights and social justice must form the legal and normative foundations upon which the Internet operates and is governed. This shall happen in a transparent and multilateral manner, based on principles of openness, inclusive participation and accountability

Chapter 2: The Charter of Human Rights and Principles for the Internet

This Charter of Human Rights and Principles for the Internet has been developed by the Dynamic Coalition on Internet Rights and Principles and draws inspiration from the Association for Progressive Communications' Internet Rights Charter and other pertinent documents. The Charter builds on the WSIS Declaration of Principles of Geneva and the Tunis Agenda for the Information Society, which both recognize that Information Communication Technologies (ICTs) present tremendous opportunities to enable individuals, communities and peoples to achieve their full potential in promoting their sustainable development and improving their quality of life. Like the WSIS Declaration, this Charter aims at building a people-centered information society, which respects and upholds fundamental human rights that are enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR). This Charter interprets and explains universal human rights standards in a new context – the Internet. The Charter re-emphasizes that human rights apply online as they do offline: human rights standards, as defined in international law, are non-negotiable. The Charter also identifies internet policy principles which are necessary to fulfill human rights in the Internet age – to support and expand the capacity of the Internet as a medium for civil, political, economic, social and cultural development. Under International law, states are legally obliged to respect, protect and fulfill the human rights of their citizens. Governments have the primary responsibility for realizing human rights within their jurisdictions. The duty to protect requires governments to protect against human rights violations committed by other actors, including businesses. States are also obliged to take appropriate steps to investigate, punish and redress human rights abuses which take place within their territory

and/or jurisdiction. However, other actors also have responsibilities under the International human rights regime. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights calls on “every individual and every organ of society” to promote and respect human rights. While these responsibilities do not equate to legal obligations (unless they have been enacted as such under national legislation) they do form part of prevailing social norms which companies and other private organizations should respect. Thus while the primary responsibilities under the Charter remain with governments, the Charter also provides guidance to governments about how they must ensure that private companies are respecting human rights, and guidelines to companies about how they should behave so as to respect human rights in the Internet environment.

PART 1. RIGHT TO ACCESS THE INTERNET

Everyone has the right to access to, and make use of, the Internet. This right underpins all other rights in this Charter. Access to and use of the Internet is increasingly indispensable for the full enjoyment of human rights including the right to freedom of expression, the right to education, the right to freedom of peaceful assembly and association, the right to take part in the government of a country, the right to work, and the right to rest and leisure. The right to access to, and make use of, the Internet derives from its integral relationship to all of these human rights. The right to access to, and make use of, the Internet shall be ensured for all and it shall not be subject to any restrictions except those which are provided by law, are necessary in a democratic society to protect national security, public order, public health or morals or the rights and freedoms of others, and are consistent with the other rights recognized in the present Charter. The right to access to, and make use of, the Internet includes:

Quality of service

The quality of service to which people are entitled access shall evolve in line with advancing technological possibilities.

Freedom of choice of system and software use

Access includes freedom of choice of system, application and software use. To facilitate this and to maintain interconnectivity and innovation, communication infrastructures and protocols should be interoperable, and standards should be open. Everyone should be able to innovate in content, applications, and services without having to undergo centralized authorization and validation procedures.

Ensuring digital inclusion

Digital inclusion requires that all people have access to, and effective use of, the range of digital media, communication platforms and devices for information management and processing. To this end active support shall be available for self-managed and other communitybased facilities and services. Public Internet access points shall be made available, such as at telecentres, libraries, community centers, clinics and schools. Access to the Internet via mobile media must also be supported.

Net neutrality and net equality

The Internet is a global commons. Its architecture must be protected and promoted for it to be a vehicle for free, open, equal and non-discriminating exchange of information, communication and culture. There should be no special privileges for, or obstacles against, any party or content on economic, social, cultural, or political grounds. This does not preclude positive discrimination to promote equity and diversity on and through the Internet.

PART 2. RIGHT TO NON-DISCRIMINATION IN INTERNET ACCESS, USE OF GOVERNANCE

As enshrined in Article 2 of the UDHR: everyone is entitled to all rights and freedoms without distinction of any kind, "such as ethnicity, color, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status". Nothing in the present Charter may be interpreted as preventing affirmative action designed at ensuring substantive equality for marginalized peoples or groups. On the Internet, the right to nondiscrimination in the enjoyment of all rights includes:

Equality of access

Certain groups in society systematically have more limited or restricted Internet access and the means and opportunities for effective use than others. This can amount to de-facto discrimination in terms of their ability to enjoy the human rights that the Internet supports. Thus efforts to increase access and effective use must recognize and address these inequalities.

Marginalized groups

The specific needs of all people in using the Internet must be addressed as part of their entitlement to dignity, to participate in social and cultural life, and to respect for their human rights. Special attention must be paid to the needs of marginalized groups including the elderly, young people, ethnic and linguistic minorities, and indigenous peoples, persons with disabilities and all sexuality and gender identities. All hardware, code, applications and content should be designed using universal design principles so that they are usable by all people, to the greatest extent possible, without the need for adaptation or specialized design. This includes the need for multiple languages and scripts to be supported.

Gender equality

Women and men have an equal right to learn about, define, access, use and shape the Internet. There must be full participation of women in all areas related to the development of the Internet to ensure gender equality

PART 3- RIGHT TO LIBERTY AND SECURITY ON THE INTERNET

As enshrined in Article 3 of the UDHR: "everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person". All security measures must be consistent with international human rights law and standards. This means that security measures will be illegal where they restrict another human right (for example the right to privacy or the right to freedom of expression) except for in exceptional circumstances. All restrictions must be precise and narrowly defined. All restrictions

must be the minimum necessary to meet a genuine need which is recognized as legal under International law, and proportionate to that need. Restrictions must also meet additional criteria which is specific to each right. No restrictions outside of these strict limits are permitted. On the Internet, the right to life, liberty and security includes

Protection against all forms of crime

Everyone shall be protected against all forms of crime committed on or using the Internet including harassment, cyber-stalking, people trafficking and misuse of one's digital identity and data.

Security of the Internet

Everyone has the right to enjoy secure connections to and on the Internet. This includes protection from services and protocols that threaten the technical functioning of the Internet, such as viruses, malware and phishing.

PART 4- RIGHT TO DEVELOPMENT THROUGH THE INTERNET

All UDHR human rights require economic, social, cultural and political development in order to be fully realized, as recognized in the UN Declaration on the Right to Development, 1986. The Internet has a vital role to play in helping to achieve the full realization of human rights, in particular in eradicating poverty, hunger, and diseases and promoting gender equality and empowerment of women. The right to development includes the full enjoyment of all rights related to the Internet and set out in this Charter. On the Internet, the right to development includes:

Poverty reduction and human development

Information and communication technologies shall be designed, developed and implemented to contribute to sustainable human development and empowerment.

Environmental sustainability

The Internet must be used in a sustainable way. This relates to the disposal of e-waste and to the use of the Internet for the protection of the environment

PART 5- FREEDOM OF EXPRESSION AND INFORMATION ON THE INTERNET

As enshrined in Article 19 of the UDHR: "everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers". As laid out in the ICCPR, the right to freedom of expression may be subject to certain restrictions, but these shall only be such as are provided by law and are necessary for respect of the rights or reputations of others; or for the protection of national security or of public order, or of public health or morals. No restrictions to the right to freedom of opinion are permissible. Freedom of expression is essential in any society for the enjoyment of other human rights and social goods including democracy and human development. On the Internet, the right to freedom of expression and information includes:

Freedom of online protest

Everyone has the right to use the Internet to organize and engage in online and offline protest.

Freedom from censorship

Everyone has the right to use the Internet without censorship in any form. This includes freedom from any measures designed to intimidate Internet users or close down expression online, including: freedom from cyber attacks and freedom from harassment online. Freedom from censorship online also includes freedom from blocking and filtering. Blocking and filtering systems which aim to prevent access to content and are not end-user controlled are a form of prior censorship and cannot be justified. Internet intermediaries must never be pressured by states or other parties to remove, hide or block content, or disclose information about Internet users.

Right to information

Everyone has the right to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through the Internet. Everybody has the right of access to make effective use of government information, which must be released in a timely and accessible manner, according national and international law.

Freedom of the media

The freedom and pluralism of the media shall be respected.

Freedom from hate speech

The beliefs and opinions of others must be respected, online as well as offline. As laid out in Article 20 of the ICCPR, “any advocacy of national, racial or religious hatred that constitutes incitement to discrimination, hostility or violence shall be prohibited by law”. Certain very specific limitations to the right to freedom of expression may be undertaken on the grounds that they cause serious injury to the human rights of others. However, this must not be used to protect abstract or subjective notions or concepts, or institutions, but rather to protect individuals and groups of people. Restrictions under this article must meet the standards for all restrictions of the right to freedom of expression as defined above.

PART 6- FREEDOM OF RELIGION AND BELIEF ON THE INTERNET

As enshrined in Article 18 of the UDHR: “everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion”. This right includes freedom, either alone or in community with others and in public or private, to manifest his or her religion or belief in teaching, practice, worship and observance. This right also includes freedom from religion. This right must not be used to illegally limit any other human rights.

PART 7-FREEDOM OF ONLINE ASSEMBLY AND ASSOCIATION

As enshrined in Article 20 of the UDHR: “everyone has the right to freedom of peaceful assembly and association. No one may be compelled to belong to an association”. On the Internet, the right to freedom of assembly and association includes:

Participation in assembly and association on the Internet

Everyone has the right to form, join, meet or visit the website or network of an assembly, group or association for any reason. Access to assemblies and associations using ICTs must not be blocked or filtered.

PART 8- RIGHT TO PRIVACY ON THE INTERNET

As enshrined in Article 12 of the UDHR: “no one shall be subjected to arbitrary or unlawful interference with their privacy, family, home or correspondence. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks”. On the Internet the right to privacy includes:

National legislation on privacy

States must establish, implement and enforce comprehensive legal frameworks to protect the privacy and personal data of citizens. These must be in line with international human rights and consumer protection standards, and must include protection from privacy violations by the state and by private companies.

Privacy policies and settings

Privacy policy and settings of all services must be easy to find, and the management of privacy settings must be comprehensive and optimized for usability.

Standards of confidentiality and integrity of IT-systems

The right to privacy must be protected by standards of confidentiality and integrity of IT-Systems, providing protection against others accessing IT-Systems without consent.

Protection of the virtual personality

Everyone has a right to a virtual personality: The virtual personality of the human person, [i.e. the personal identification in information systems] is inviolable. Digital signatures, user names, passwords, PIN and TAN codes must not be used or changed by others without the consent of the owner. The virtual personality of human persons must be respected. However, the right to a virtual personality must not be misused to the detriment of others.

Right to anonymity and to use encryption

Every individual has the right to communicate anonymously on the Internet. Everyone has the right to use encryption technology to ensure secure, private and anonymous communication.

Freedom from surveillance

Everyone has the freedom to communicate without arbitrary surveillance or interception (including behavioral tracking, profiling, and cyber-stalking), or the threat of surveillance or interception. Any agreement regarding access to online services that includes acceptance of surveillance shall clearly state the nature of the surveillance.

Freedom from defamation

No one shall be subjected to unlawful attacks on their honour and reputation on the Internet. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks.

However protection of reputation must not be used as an excuse to limit the right to Freedom of Expression beyond the narrow limits of permitted restrictions

PART 9- RIGHT TO DIGITAL DATA PROTECTION

As enshrined in Art 12 of the UDHR everyone has the right to privacy. An important aspect of this right is that everyone has the right to protection of personal data concerning him or her. On the Internet, the right to protection of personal data includes:

Protection of personal data

Fair information practices should be enacted into national law to place obligations on companies and governments who collect and process personal data, and give rights to those individuals whose personal data is collected.

Obligations of data collectors

The collection, use, disclosure and retention of personal data must all meet transparent privacy-protecting standards. Everyone has the right to exercise control over the personal data collected about them and its usage. Whoever requires personal data from persons, shall request the individual's informed consent regarding the content, purposes, storage location, duration and mechanisms for access, retrieval and correction of their personal data. Everyone has a right to access, retrieve and delete the personal data collected about them.

Minimum standards on use of personal data

When personal information is required, only the minimum data necessary must be collected and for the minimum period of time for which this is required. Data must be deleted when it is no longer necessary for the purposes for which it was collected. Data collectors have an obligation to seek active consent and to notify people when their information has been forwarded to third parties, abused, lost, or stolen. Appropriate security measures shall be taken for the protection of personal data stored in automated data files against accidental or unauthorized destruction or accidental loss as well as against unauthorized access, alteration or dissemination.

Monitoring by independent data protection authorities

Data protection should be monitored by independent data protection authorities, which work transparently and without commercial advantage or political influence.

PART 10- RIGHT TO EDUCATION ON AND ABOUT THE INTERNET

As enshrined in article 26 of the UDHR: "everyone has the right to education". Everyone has the right to be educated about the Internet and to use the Internet for education. On the Internet the right to education includes:

Education through the Internet

Virtual learning environments and other sorts of multimedia, learning and teaching platforms shall take into account local and regional variations in terms of language, pedagogy and knowledge-traditions. Publications, research, text books, course materials and other kinds of learning materials shall be published as Open Educational Resources with the right to freely

use, copy, reuse, adapt, translate and redistribute them. Free or low-cost training opportunities, methodologies and materials related to using the Internet for social development shall be promoted.

Education about the Internet and human rights

Everyone shall be educated about the Internet Education on the Internet shall include raising awareness and respect for human rights (online and offline). Digital literacy shall be a key component of education. Knowledge and skills enable people to use and shape the Internet to meet their needs.

PART 11- RIGHT TO CULTURE AND ACCESS TO KNOWLEDGE ON THE INTERNET

As enshrined in Article 27 of the UDHR: “everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits”. Also enshrined in Article 27 of the UDHR: “everyone has the right to the protection of the moral and material interests resulting from any scientific, literary or artistic production” of which he or she is author. Intellectual property is a social product and has a social function. Thus, intellectual property protection must balance the rights of creators with the public interest. Copyright regimes must not disproportionately restrict the capacity of the Internet to support public access to knowledge and culture. On the Internet the right to freely participate in culture includes:

Right to participate in the cultural life of the community

Everyone has the right to use the Internet to access knowledge, information and research. Everyone has the freedom to access and share information of public value without being subject to harassment or limitations. Everyone has the right to make use of the knowledge and instruments of the past to enhance the personal and collective knowledge of the future.

Diversity of languages and cultures

The public service value of the Internet shall be protected, including access to quality and diverse information as well as different cultural content. The Internet shall represent a diversity of cultures and languages in terms of appearance and functionality. Cultural and linguistic diversity on the Internet must be realized in all forms (e.g. text, images and sound). Technological evolution and innovation to promote diversity on the Internet shall be promoted. Indigenous knowledge shall be protected and promoted online.

Right to use one’s own language

All individuals and communities have the right to use their own language to create, disseminate, and share information and knowledge through the Internet. Special attention shall be given to promoting access for minority languages. This includes promotion of the technology and content required to access and use domain names, software, services and content in minority languages and scripts.

Freedom from restrictions of access to knowledge by licensing and copyright

Creators have the right to be remunerated and acknowledged for their work and innovations. However, this must be achieved in ways which do not restrict further innovation or access to public and educational knowledge and resources. Licensing and copyright of content must permit knowledge to be created, shared, used and built upon. Permissive licensing models shall be used. Internationally accepted 'fair use' exceptions and limitations to copyright must be used, including making copies for personal and classroom use, format conversion, library lending, review, critique, satire, research and sampling. Techniques which prevent 'fair use' exceptions must be prohibited.

Knowledge commons and the public domain

Publicly funded research and intellectual and cultural work must be made available freely to the general public, where possible.

Free/open source software and open standards

Open standards and open formats must be made available. Free/libre and Open Source Software (FOSS) must be used, promoted and implemented in public and educational institutions and services. When a free solution or open standards do not exist, the development of the needed software shall be promoted.

PART 12- RIGHTS OF CHILDREN AND THE INTERNET

Children are entitled to all of the rights in the present Charter. Furthermore, as enshrined in Article 25 of the UDHR: childhood is "entitled to special care and assistance". As enshrined in Article 5 of the CRC young people are entitled to respect for their "evolving capacities". In terms of the Internet this means that children must both be given the freedom to use the Internet, and also protected from the dangers associated with the Internet. The balance between these priorities shall depend on the young person's capabilities. The State must respect the rights and responsibilities of parents and the extended family to provide guidance for the child which is appropriate to her or his evolving capacities. On the internet the right to special care and assistance and respect for evolving capacities of children includes:

Right to benefit from the Internet

Children should be able to benefit from the Internet according to their age. Children must have opportunities to use the Internet to exercise their civil, political, economic, cultural and social rights. These include rights to health, education, privacy, access to information, freedom of expression and freedom of association.

Freedom from exploitation and child abuse imagery

Children have a right to grow up and develop in a safe environment that is free from sexual or other kinds of exploitation. Steps must therefore be taken to prevent the use of the Internet to violate the rights of children, including through trafficking and child abuse imagery. However, such measures must be narrowly targeted and proportionate. The effect of measures taken on the free flow of information online must be given due consideration.

Right to have views heard

Children who are capable of forming their own views have the right to express them in all Internet policy matters that affect them, and their views shall be given due weight according to their age and maturity.

Best interests of the child

As enshrined in Article 3 of the CRC: “in all actions concerning children, whether undertaken by public or private social welfare institutions, courts of law, administrative authorities or legislative bodies, the best interests of the child shall be a primary consideration”.

PART 13- RIGHTS OF PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES AND THE INTERNET

People with disabilities are entitled to all of the rights in the present Charter. As enshrined in Article 4 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), “States Parties undertake to ensure and promote the full realisation of all human rights and fundamental freedoms for all persons with disabilities without discrimination of any kind on the basis of disability”. The Internet is important in enabling persons with disabilities to fully enjoy all human rights and fundamental freedoms. Special measures must be taken to ensure that the Internet is accessible, available and affordable. On the Internet, the rights of people with disabilities include:

Accessibility to the Internet

Persons with disabilities have a right to access, on an equal basis with others, to the Internet. Such access must be promoted through: the development, promulgation and monitoring of minimum standards and guidelines for accessibility; the provision of training on accessibility issues facing persons with disabilities; and the promotion of other appropriate forms of assistance to people with disabilities to ensure their access to information.

Availability and affordability of the Internet

Steps must be taken to ensure the availability and effective use of the Internet by people with disabilities. Research and development must be undertaken to promote the availability of Information and Communications Technologies in a format suitable for persons with disabilities. Priority should be given to developing technologies at an affordable cost. Persons with disabilities have the right to accessible information about assistive technologies, as well as other forms of assistance, support, services and facilities.

PART 14- RIGHT TO WORK AND THE INTERNET

As enshrined in Article 23 of the UDHR: “everyone has the right to work”. On the Internet, the right to work includes:

Respect for workers’ rights

Everyone has the right to use the Internet to form trade unions, including the right to promote one’s own interests and gather in freely elected organs of representation.

Internet at the workplace

Workers and employees shall have Internet access at their work place, where available. Any restrictions on Internet use in the work place shall be explicitly stated in staff or organizational policies. The terms and conditions for surveillance of the Internet use of employees must be clearly stated in work place policies and comply with the right to data protection.

Work on and through the Internet

All people shall have the right to seek employment and to work through or by means of the Internet.

PART 15- RIGHT TO ONLINE PARTICIPATION IN PUBLIC AFFAIRS

As enshrined in Article 21 of the UDHR: “everyone has the right to take part in the government of his [or her] country, directly or through freely chosen representatives”. On the Internet the right to take part in the government of one’s country includes:

Right to equal access to electronic services

Article 21 of the UDHR also states that “everyone has the right of equal access to public service in the country”. Everyone has the right to equal access to electronic services in his country.

Right to participate in electronic government

Where electronic government is available, everyone must have the right to participate.

PART 16- RIGHTS TO CONSUMER PROTECTION ON THE INTERNET

Everyone must respect, protect and fulfill principles of consumer protection on the Internet. E-Commerce must be regulated to ensure that consumers receive the same level of protection as they enjoy in non-electronic transactions.

PART 17- RIGHTS TO HEALTH AND SOCIAL SERVICES ON THE INTERNET

As enshrined in Article 25 of the UDHR: “Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and wellbeing of himself [or herself] and of his [or her] family, and necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond his [or her] control”. On the Internet the right to a standard of living adequate for health includes:

Access to health-related content online

Everyone shall have access to health-related and social services on the Internet.

PART 18- RIGHT TO LEGAL REMEDY AND FAIR TRIAL FOR ACTION INVOLVING THE INTERNET

Right to a legal remedy

As enshrined in Article 8 of the UDHR: “everyone has the right to an effective remedy by the competent national tribunals for acts violating the fundamental rights granted him [or her] by the constitution or by law”.

Right to a fair trial

As enshrined in Article 10 of the UDHR: “everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his [or her] rights and obligations and of any criminal charge against him [or her]”. Criminal trials must follow fair trial standards as defined by the UDHR (Articles 9–11) and the ICCPR (Articles 9 and 14–16) as well as other pertinent documents. It is increasingly common for the right to a fair trial and to an effective remedy to be violated in the Internet environment, for example with Internet intermediary companies being asked to make judgements about whether content is illegal and encouraged to remove content without a court order. It is therefore necessary to reiterate that procedural rights must be respected, protected and fulfilled on the Internet as they are offline.

Right to due process

Everyone has the right to due process in relation to any legal claims or possible violations of the law regarding the Internet.

PART 19- RIGHT TO APPROPRIATE SOCIAL AND INTERNATIONAL ORDER FOR THE INTERNET

As enshrined in Article 28 of the UDHR: “Everyone is entitled to a social and international order in which the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration can be fully realized”. On the Internet the right to an appropriate social and international order includes:

Governance of the Internet for human rights

The Internet and the communications system must be governed in such a way as to ensure that it upholds and expands human rights to the fullest extent possible. Internet governance must be driven by principles of openness, inclusiveness and accountability and exercised in transparent and multilateral manner.

Multilingualism and pluralism on the Internet

The Internet as a social and international order shall enshrine principles of multilingualism, pluralism, and heterogeneous forms of cultural life in both form and substance.

Effective participation in Internet governance

Everyone has the right to participate in the governance of the Internet. The interests of all those affected by a policy or decision shall be represented in the governance processes, which shall enable all to participate in its development. Full and effective participation of all, in particular disadvantaged groups in global, regional and national decision-making must be ensured.

Chapter 3: Budapest Convention Precedence Detected Under the Council of Europe**Azerbaijan**

In order to analyze the digital situation in Azerbaijan, this section will be comprised of four smaller subsections. The four stages describes are: (1) Overview, (2) Obstacle to Access, (3) Limits on Content and (4) Violations of User Rights

(1) Overview

Internet freedom in Azerbaijan deteriorated during the coverage period. The state remains in control of the information and communication technology (ICT) sector, which was evident in its decision to throttle access to the internet and block social media platforms for 46 days during the conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh. Infrastructural challenges, which saw little to no improvement, kept internet connections of low quality and out of reach for many. Those who voice dissent online can expect prosecution if they reside in Azerbaijan, and risk intimidation from authorities and progovernment trolls if abroad. During the coverage period, scores of activists were prosecuted over online criticism of the government's policies, antiwar sentiment, and other activism. Independent journalists continued to face persecution by law enforcement and the State Security Service.

Power in Azerbaijan's authoritarian regime remains heavily concentrated in the hands of Ilham Aliyev, who has served as president since 2003, and his extended family. Corruption is rampant, and the formal political opposition has been weakened by years of persecution. Between September 27 and November 10, Azerbaijani and Armenian forces engaged in military operations over the disputed Nagorno-Karabakh territory, with the Azerbaijani government ultimately reclaiming control over much of the area previously held by ethnic Armenian forces allied with the government in Yerevan. During the 44-day war, the government of Azerbaijan deliberately cut off access to much of the internet, saying the actions were necessary to prevent the spread of Armenian provocations online. However, government websites and online news platforms affiliated with the government were accessible, aside from a brief disruption.

(2) Obstacle to Access

Poor ICT infrastructure and state ICT monopolies are key obstacles to improving internet access and service quality across Azerbaijan. According to the Economist Intelligence Unit's 2021 Inclusive Internet Index, around 78 percent of households have access to the internet. This relatively high penetration rate obscures disparities in access, as well as slow connection speeds.

Although internet speed in Azerbaijan improved over the past year, it continues to lag behind other countries. The government's Strategic Roadmap for Telecommunication and Information Technology Development sought to increase the average fixed-broadband speed to 20 Mbps by 2020, and according to the internet-metrics company Ookla, this goal was achieved as the average reached 23.6 Mbps in January 2021. However, in 2019–20 the broadband-research company Cable recorded the mean broadband download speed in Azerbaijan at just 4.89 Mbps.

According to the 2021 Inclusive Internet Index, Azerbaijan is home to 19.3 fixed-broadband internet subscriptions per 100 people, and 107 mobile-phone subscriptions per 100 people.

Both second-generation (2G) and third-generation (3G) mobile networks cover virtually all the population, while fourth-generation (4G) networks cover about half. In July 2020, in partnership

with Nokia, leading mobile operator Azercell expanded its 4G geographic coverage, focusing on semiurban and rural regions.

According to the *Mobile Economy Russia & CIS Report*—released in 2020 by GSMA, a London-based industry group representing mobile operators worldwide—Azerbaijan is expected to join the 5G network by 2023. In November 2019, Azercell piloted 5G services in Baku’s city center for a short time. In December 2019, Azercell and Sweden-based Ericsson signed a three-year Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) planning the joint deployment of 5G projects, trials, and use cases in Azerbaijan. According to the MoU, Azercell plans to extend the pilot zone, offering the service beyond the city center. In June 2020, the Ministry for Transportation, Communication, and High Technologies (MTCHT) acknowledged that 5G was not currently in use in Azerbaijan. No further explanation was provided by the ministry about the road map to introduce 5G in Azerbaijan.

Users mainly access the internet via mobile devices, followed by home, work, and Wi-Fi hotspot connections. In 2017, MTCHT initiated a plan to establish free Wi-Fi hotspots in public parks and around central locations in Baku. In 2019, Wi-Fi hotspots had been installed in some 20 parks. In June 2020, Azerbaijan Railways announced plans to introduce Wi-Fi access on all internal train routes.

Users report regular connectivity problems. Some claim that internet service providers (ISPs) cut off connections because they cannot accommodate high demand. Providers say this is not the case, often blaming disruptions on “prophylactic work” carried out on servers. Others claim that ISPs intentionally throttle connections in compliance with government requests (see A3). Osman Gunduz of the Azerbaijan Internet Forum noted that bandwidth designated for a single user is often divided and sold to multiple users. He also attributed the lack of fast internet access in the country to the lack of competition.

Widespread internet blackouts have also occurred every few years in Azerbaijan.

Internet access is somewhat expensive relative to monthly incomes, and Azerbaijan continues to lag behind neighboring countries where faster connections are available at comparatively lower costs. Given the extent to which the ICT sector is controlled by the state, the MTCHT—not the market—sets prices. For example, in May 2019, backbone provider Delta Telecom announced a 70 percent discount on its services, but downstream ISPs did not cut their prices accordingly, on the alleged instructions of the MTCHT.

According to the Economist Intelligence Unit’s 2021 Inclusive Internet Index, the monthly cost of a fixed internet connection is 1.7 percent of gross national income (GNI) per capita, while the cost of a mobile data plan offering 1 GB per month is .7 percent of GNI per capita. Price data from the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) put the monthly cost of a fixed internet connection at 1.54 percent of GNI per capita in 2020, and the cost of a mobile data plan offering 1.5 GB per month at 0.92 percent of GNI per capita that year. In 2020, Azerbaijan’s GNI per capita was the equivalent of \$4,450, per the World Bank. Official statistics indicate that the average prices of “communications services” and “internet services” increased from 2018 to 2020.

In Azerbaijan, there is a digital divide in terms of geography. According to the official figures from 2019, household internet access rates were 74.9 percent in rural areas, and 82.7 percent in urban areas. Despite government pledges, ICT infrastructure beyond Baku is neglected, and

the capital is the overwhelming beneficiary of state investment in ICT. The rural-urban divide became even more visible during the COVID-19 pandemic as Azerbaijan adopted distance learning on March 3, 2020. Students, families, and teachers alike complained of inadequate infrastructure, lack of available personal devices at home, and expensive internet.

According to official figures from 2018, younger people are much more likely to be internet users than older people, and wealthier families are much more likely to own computers than poorer families. Moreover, there is a gendered dimension to inequalities in internet access: the gap between internet use among men and women is 12 percent, according to the 2021 Inclusive Internet Index. Low ICT literacy also remains a problem.

The government exercises control over internet infrastructure. During the coverage period, authorities intentionally restricted connectivity for 46 days, which was Azerbaijan's longest network disruption to date.

On September 27, the day full-scale war erupted between Azerbaijani and Armenian forces in Nagorno-Karabakh, the MTCHT throttled mobile and fixed-line broadband internet across Azerbaijan and blocked a number of social media platforms and websites, including Facebook, WhatsApp, and Skype. The action lasted 46 days—Azerbaijan's longest internet disruption to date (See B1).

The MTCHT did not mention the duration of the outage or which services would be blocked in the country until October 12 when Gunel Gozalova, a spokesperson for the MTCHT, stated that the ministry was restricting the internet “simply to prevent unwanted, unverified, war-related content on social networks” (see B3). In a November 11 statement, the MTCHT announced the lifting of restrictions on internet access effective the following day. Throughout the 46-day period, Azerbaijani internet providers and telecom companies shared no information on how they intended to handle these government orders. Some companies informed their clients that their websites and mobile applications would not be accessible if a virtual private network (VPN) was in active use on the user's device. During the network disruption, mobile operators and the Special State Security Service encouraged Azerbaijan citizens to refrain from using VPN services at all times when trying to access social media platforms, citing user privacy as a reason. There are no restrictions on VPN use in the country otherwise.

Beginning in April 2020, Ali Karimli, leader of the opposition Popular Front party, and his family experienced a prolonged fixed- and mobile-internet outage, which continued through the coverage period. The outage appeared to be a targeted, individualized disruption. On January 18, 2021, Karimli and his spouse, Samara Seyidova, said they were taking the case to the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) after having received no response from domestic courts, but in June 2021 they had yet to hear if the case would be accepted.

Previous disruptions were reported by opposition activists who complained about connectivity issues in the hours before opposition rallies were set to begin. Residents in the vicinity of these rallies have also experienced connectivity issues for the duration of these events. Local ISPs argue that the disruptions are directly connected to the number and density of users gathered in one place. Technology analyst and current Azerbaijan Internet Forum president Osman Gunduz says this practice is a violation of existing laws and that if a rally is authorized, all relevant actors including government agencies and ISPs, should ensure uninterrupted connectivity.

However, the political opposition is often denied authorization to hold rallies. As a result, unsanctioned rallies are common. Regardless of a rally's legality, though, the authorities can arbitrarily disrupt connectivity, according to Zohrab Ismayil, director of the Public Association for Assistance to Free Economy, a local nongovernmental organization (NGO). At the government's request, ISPs will cut off connectivity at any location, as an informal condition of doing business in the country.

The MTCHT holds significant shares in a number of leading ISPs, and the government is authorized to instruct companies to cut internet service under broadly defined circumstances. President Ilham Aliyev declared martial law for the entire territory of Azerbaijan on September 27, 2020 (see C1), with the approval of Parliament. The designation, which came into effect on September 28, enabled the MTCHT in coordination with military authorities to restrict individuals' and legal entities' connection to the general telecommunication networks. It further granted the MTCHT the authority to disconnect telephone lines from the network and suspend provision of internet services for the purpose of meeting the needs of military authorities. Martial law was ultimately lifted on December 11, 2020.

Wholesale access to international gateways is maintained by companies with close ties to the government. Only two ISPs, AzerTelecom and Delta Telecom, are licensed to connect to international internet traffic. Delta Telecom owns the internet backbone and is the main distributor of traffic to other ISPs. It controls the country's sole internet exchange point (IXP)

The ICT market in Azerbaijan is fairly concentrated in the hands of the government. The absence of regulatory reform also inhibits the development of the sector, though the government's Strategic Roadmap for Telecommunication and Information Technology Development calls for the removal of the commercial authority currently exercised by the MTCHT.

The fixed-line broadband market lacks equality between operators. Many ISPs are present in the market, including three state-owned providers: Aztelekom, Baktelecom (BTC), and AzDataCom. According to the Asian Development Bank, state-owned companies ultimately control about 50 percent of the market. In addition to being state owned, Aztelekom, the largest ISP operating outside Baku, has ownership ties to the family of President Ilham Aliyev.

There are three major players in Azerbaijan's mobile service market: Azercell, Azerfon (operating under the brand "Nar"), and Bakcell. Azercell is the leading mobile service provider, with a market share of about 49 percent. Bakcell and Azerfon follow behind, self-reporting 3 million and 2.3 million subscribers, respectively. Both Azercell and Azerfon are connected to the Aliyev family, and in 2018, the government formally assumed ownership of Azercell. Bakcell is privately held by businessman Nasib Hasanov.

Mobile operators must obtain a technical license from the government in order to do business. These licenses are issued for a period of 10 years. There is no licensing regime for other ISPs, but they must register with the MTCHT. If they fail to do so, they will face fines. Some providers have raised concerns with the MTCHT over the lack of transparency in the registration process, as well as the sensitivity of the information they must submit as part of it. The MTCHT claims that registration is carried out in accordance with the law, and has dismissed concerns about improper data retention.

The government has a major role in controlling the ICT sector through state-owned companies and government institutions. Service providers are regulated by the MTCHT, whose leadership is beholden to Aliyev. The former Ministry of Communications and High Technologies was dissolved in 2017 and merged with the Ministry of Transport, creating the MTCHT.

Local civil society groups like the Azerbaijan Internet Forum have been critical of the MTCHT's stewardship of the ICT sector. Osman Gunduz argues that the MTCHT has abused its regulatory and commercial powers to stymie private business, to the detriment of the ICT sector.

(3) Limits on Content

During the coverage period, the government restricted access to a number of social media sites and it continued to restrict access to additional websites, particularly those associated with the opposition or those that investigate politically sensitive topics such as official corruption.

On September 26, the MTHCT blocked access to Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, YouTube, TikTok, LinkedIn, Twitter, Zoom and Skype during the Nagorno-Karabakh war, with the blockage lasting 46 days. The government justified the action as a means “to prevent unwanted, unverified, war-related content on social networks.” According to reporting from Bloomberg, Sandvine Inc., a Canada-based company backed by a US-based private equity firm, worked with the Azerbaijani government—namely, the government-controlled backbone provider Delta Telecom—to “urgently” install Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) technology to block live streaming to YouTube, Facebook, and Instagram. Since at least March 2017, the government has used DPI technology to block websites.

According to the most recent measurements conducted by the Open Observatory for Network Interference (OONI), at least nine websites present signs of blocking as of April 2021. They include online news sites Azerbaijan Saadi, 24saat.org, Abzas.net, *Azadliq*, Azadliq Radio (the Azerbaijan language service for RFE/RL), Gununsesi, Kanal 13 TV, Meydan TV, as well as the Organized Crime and Corruption Reporting Project (OCCRP).

In May 2020, investigative journalist Khadija Ismayilova reported that the MTCHT was seeking court approval to restrict users' ability to access news websites already blocked in the country (namely, the newspaper *Azadliq*, Azadliq Radio, Meydan TV, and Turan TV) via Facebook, other social media platforms, and VPNs. These websites were initially blocked in March 2017 for allegedly threatening national security and hosting content that promoted “violence, hatred, or extremism” and “violated privacy or constituted slander.” A ruling in the MTCHT's favor may legally oblige Facebook and other companies to prevent Azerbaijani users from seeing content from these websites. The authorities could also instruct ISPs to block these websites' social media profiles, which would practically entail blocking entire social media platforms. During the coverage period, no steps were taken in this direction.

Ahead of the February 2020 snap parliamentary elections, local news website Yuksəliş Naminə was blocked after publishing stories highlighting corruption in the city of Sumgayit. Reportedly, independent news website Basta, which was previously restricted in July 2018, was also blocked.

In April 2019, a court in Baku upheld a decision to block Meydan TV, which is based in Berlin, Germany. Meydan TV was first blocked in 2017, on the grounds that its stories were “detrimental to the interests of the state.”

In April 2019, the government restricted access to Arqument.az, but it was accessible during the coverage period. The outlet was previously blocked in August 2018, along with Az24saat.org, Monitortv.info, and Xural.com, but it had won a rare reprieve from a judge. The order to block the websites came after the outlets' editors refused to take down stories that allegedly defamed public officials.

Gununsesi.info, a website operated by former political prisoner Parviz Hashimli, was previously blocked in August 2018. Hashimli was stopped that month at the Azerbaijan-Georgia border while traveling with his father. He was informed that he was subject to a travel ban, and police interrogated him over 10 articles published on his website. In August 2019, Hashimli's travel ban was lifted. In December 2019, Sweden-based NGO Qurium reported that the website remained blocked by means of DPI.

In 2018, Bakcell rolled out a free roaming email service for corporate users, relying on Sandvine's technology, allowing Bakcell to "get a more detailed view of network traffic," and "limit malicious or unwanted traffic for subscribers." The same year, Qurium media identified that at least one of the internet protocol (IP) addresses engaged in blocking of websites in Azerbaijan was linked to Bestcomp Group, a Baku-based supplier of DPI technology.

Throughout the coverage period, all government websites and online news platforms affiliated with the government were accessible, and their social media accounts as well as Telegram channels worked—aside from a brief disruption during the Nagorno-Karabakh war.

During the coverage period, authorities continued using threats and other forms of pressure to force the removal of online content.

In January 2021, the police questioned Elmir Abbasov, an activist with civic movement NIDA, over a Facebook post in which he criticized President Aliyev over the economy's dependence on hydrocarbons. Abbasov was told to remove the post, which he did. According to Azerbaijan Internet Watch, another journalist, whose name was withheld to protect their safety, said that they were also told to delete a Facebook post describing an instance of police corruption.

Authorities pressured users to remove online content related to the COVID-19 pandemic that painted the government in an unfavorable light. In March 2020, Amina Mammadova, a reporter for online news website Toplum TV, was questioned by the police sharing a friend's Facebook post claiming that bribes could be paid to escape pandemic-related quarantine measures. She unshared the post. Also in March 2020, Facebook user Bakhtiyar Mammadli was forced by the police to remove a post about movement restrictions in Baku that he claimed was a joke. Opposition figure Rza Safarsoy was instructed to remove a Facebook post highlighting the lack of state support for unemployed people during the pandemic in April 2020. That month, police in the city of Shirvan asked Kanal24.az journalist Ibrahim Vazirov to delete several video reports; they detained him when he refused to do so. Similarly, a member of the opposition Azerbaijan Democracy and Welfare Movement was jailed for 15 days after refusing to remove Facebook posts criticizing the government's response to the pandemic.

In February 2020, graphic designer Rasul Hasanov was detained after sharing a video edited to show Azerbaijani riot police outside the Central Election Commission (CEC) performing a traditional dance (The riot police had been called in to cordon off the CEC's headquarters as defeated candidates and their supporters gathered outside demanding annulment of the

February 2020 snap parliamentary vote). Police removed the video from his Facebook profile against his will as they questioned him. Afterwards, he was released.

In December 2019, rapper Parviz Guluzade (known by his stage name Paster) was sentenced to 30 days in administrative detention shortly after he posted a music video on YouTube for a song mentioning Pasha Bank, which belongs to the president's two daughters. The video was removed, and Paster served 30 days in administrative detention. Mehman Huseynov, a popular blogger and former political prisoner, was beaten after staging a protest rally in support of Paster on December 27, 2019.

In May 2019, Ali Mammadov, an Azerbaijani dissident living in Germany, was coerced into deleting antigovernment Facebook posts after Azerbaijani police threatened to detain a family member who was still living in the country.

Content from Azerbaijani users is frequently removed or restricted. Toward the end of 2019, online news websites Arqument.az and Anaxeber.info reported that their websites' URLs had been banned by Facebook without prior notification; thus, links to these websites could not be shared on the platform. Similarly, Meydan TV, was not notified when photos and videos the outlet shared from protests in Baku in October 2019 were removed from Facebook. Arqument.az and Anaxeber.info's URLs were later unbanned (Facebook claimed it had banned them by mistake), while none of Meydan TV's deleted content was restored. Similarly, Komanda.az was banned by Facebook without prior notification in May 2020. Following an intervention, the website's URL was permitted again. The government did not ask Facebook to remove any content in the second half of 2020.

Between July 2020 and December 2020, Twitter received 16 removal requests from the government, complying with 57 percent of them. Google received 9 takedown requests (on defamation, hate speech, fraud, copyright, privacy, and national security grounds from the government in the second half of of 2020, and complied with 27.3 percent of them.

In March 2020, several videos on the YouTube channel of the news outlet Azadliq were blocked in response to falsified takedown requests. Similarly, videos were removed from France-based journalist Natig Adilov's YouTube channel. The international NGO Access Now helped both parties recover their videos. In December 2019 and January 2020, a YouTube channel run by Shakir Zade, an activist living abroad, was disabled three times by government-backed media outlets that misused the platform's copyright infringement reporting mechanism. In 2019, the government targeted the YouTube channels of AzadSoz and HamamTimes in this way.

Decisions to block websites or otherwise censor the internet in Azerbaijan are arbitrary and politicized, clearly targeting independent and opposition-affiliated news websites that are critical of the government. Court approval is not required before officially blocking a website, but it must be sought after the fact. Observers have noted that the courts are not independent and are unlikely to provide genuine oversight. There is no meaningful avenue for appeal, and no information on the total number of websites blocked at any given time. Under Article 13.3.6 of the Law on Information, Informatization, and Information Protection, the MTCHT is required to maintain a list of court-approved blocks on websites, but the ministry is currently in violation of this provision.

During the 46-day throttling of the internet and blocking of social media platforms in 2020, Gunel Gozalova, a spokesperson for the MTCHT, stated that the government had blocked access to

these websites “simply to prevent unwanted, unverified, war-related content on social networks,” more than two weeks after the blocking was initiated (see A3).

Additionally, the Martial Law (see A3 and C1), which took effect from September to December 2020, allowed the government to restrict or suspend the activities of mass media, including online media.

In January 2021, President Aliyev signed a decree “on deepening media reforms in the republic of Azerbaijan,” which transferred the authority of the State Support Fund for Mass Media Development to the newly established Azerbaijani Agency for Media Development (AAMD). The AAMD will have the authority to “take measures to protect state and commercial secrets” and to alert authorities when it detects a violation of the restrictive code of administrative offenses (see C2). Critics are concerned that the agency could further inhibit the work of independent and opposition media platforms. Under the decree, the government also began drafting a new law on media.

Recent legislative changes have further codified the state’s power to compel a website owner to take down certain information. In March 2020, amid the COVID-19 outbreak, the parliament amended the Law on Information, Informatization, and Information Protection to expand the definition of “prohibited information” to encompass false information endangering human life and health, as well as “causing significant property damage; mass violation of public safety; disruption of life support facilities, financial, transport, communications, industrial, energy and social infrastructure facilities; or leading to other socially dangerous consequences.”

In December 2017, amendments were approved that empower authorities to “restrict access” to “prohibited information” on the internet or otherwise impose fines for distributing such content. In March 2017, the Law on Information, Informatization, and Information Protection was amended to define “prohibited information” as content that, among other things, promotes extremism, separatism, or terrorism; calls for public disorder; constitutes a state secret; conveys hate speech; insults or defames; violates copyright; glorifies suicide; or contains information related to illegal drugs, gambling, weaponry, or pornography. This change also empowered the MTCHT to block “prohibited information” when a website owner fails to remove it within eight hours of receiving notification.

Content that reveals personal information without consent may be subject to removal under Articles 5.7 and 7.2 of the Law on Personal Data. A written demand from the individual concerned, a court, or the executive branch is required. Authorities can also remove online content in cases of defamation.

ISPs are immune from intermediary liability. However, they assume liability if they ignore court orders to block specific web resources.

Policies that govern whether content about or from Azerbaijan is removed from popular, privately owned social media platforms—especially Facebook and YouTube—are opaque. They sometimes lead to the removal of content protected under international human rights standards (see B2).

In June 2020, speaking at a parliament session, member of the New Azerbaijan Party (YAP), Siyavush Novruz, said Azerbaijan should create its own mechanism to control social media platforms.

The long-running government crackdown against independent and opposition media, combined with arrests of online political activists, has significantly limited the space for free expression. Some bloggers and journalists have resorted to self-censorship, especially if they are employed by state or progovernment media. Mehman Aliyev, the director of Azerbaijan's independent in-country wire service, the Turan Information Agency, says self-censorship is pervasive and comes from fear of retribution.

Self-censorship is pervasive even among ordinary social media users, who are aware that they may face criminal charges for their expression online. However, users can and do criticize government policies on social media platforms, which has sometimes proven effective in changing the course of official decision-making (see B8).

The government attempts to tightly control the online information landscape, limiting the public's access to unfavorable news. Many online outlets spread progovernment propaganda, in violation of the Law on Mass Media and the Code of Professional Ethics for Journalists. This tendency was on full display during the COVID-19 pandemic, as progovernment online outlets blanketed the Azerbaijani internet with letters praising the leadership of President Ilham Aliyev, ostensibly written by grateful citizens.

Similarly, during the military conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh, much of the media landscape in Azerbaijan was dominated by positive coverage of the government and, specifically, the president. Footage widely circulated online both by government sources and government-affiliated media showed destruction of Armenia's military equipment and Azerbaijani soldiers marching in formation, followed by patriotic text, as well as celebrations by viewers in the country and outside.

Government officials and institutions, notably the MTCHT, pressure independent and opposition online outlets, editors, and journalists to remove specific content (see B2). Often this content pertains to social grievances or government officials' involvement in illegal activities. During the COVID-19 pandemic, watchdog NGO Reporters Without Borders (RSF) observed that journalists were "under pressure just to use the official information provided by the special COVID-19 unit that the government created." The NGO also noted that ordinary social media users were warned not to share "fake news."

Progovernment commentators, including automated bots, continue to distort discussions online. For example, an investigation published by the *Guardian* in April 2021 demonstrated how Facebook allowed a troll network linked to YAP, the ruling party, to return to the platform. The network, which was initially removed in October 2020 after former Facebook researcher Sophie Zhang informed company executives about its existence in August 2019, used Facebook to target news outlets Azad Soz, Mikroskop Media, Radio Free Europe, and Abzas.net, and political opposition parties, including the Azerbaijan Popular Front party (APFP).

In March 2021, another investigation revealed how Berlin-based independent news platform Meydan TV was targeted by hundreds of Facebook accounts that accused the news outlet of distributing pro-Armenian propaganda after it had posted a call for applications for a media literacy project. MikroskopMedia, an online platform based in the Latvian capital, Riga, was targeted in a similar way when it posted content on Facebook that was critical of the Azerbaijan's government. In all of these examples, accounts appeared to be Facebook profiles, but were fake pages used to dilute the content shared by these platforms and to attempt to create a perception of trust in and support for the government of Azerbaijan.

Such content manipulation efforts were pioneered by the presidential adviser Ali Hasanov, known as the “King of Trolls.” This trend continued even after Hasanov was dismissed from his job in November 2019. During snap parliamentary elections held in February 2020, monitors observed that “progovernment bots and trolls were active in comment sections.” Prominent activists are often harassed by trolls, as are independent and opposition journalists (see C7). A July 2019 report from the Index on Censorship observed that “the comments sections of YouTube videos posted to OsmanqiziTV, MeydanTV, and other critical channels are full of comments from people with fake names and accounts. These comments often contain threats, insults, inane arguments, or praise for the ruling regime.”

The AAMD, which was created following a January 2021 decree from President Aliyev, will play an active role in funding the media and “implementing projects that are important for the state and society” (see B3). Critics are concerned that the AAMD will attempt to exert control over the media, just as its predecessor, the State Support Fund for Mass Media Development, did over the last decade.

The limits imposed on independent or opposition media make it difficult for them to attract advertising to sustain their work. The 2019 IREX Media Sustainability Index found that most independent or opposition media “do not consider advertising due to existing political pressures.” Companies are reluctant to support these outlets due to the risk that they will lose their business licenses or face other reprisals from the government. Election monitors from the Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe (OSCE) reported that they were informed “about harassment of advertisers who sponsor private media.”

Laws regulating foreign funding of NGOs have made it easier for the government to target local civic groups and media outlets that receive grants from outside sources. In 2015, President Aliyev signed amendments to the Law on Mass Media that allow courts to order the closure of any media outlet that receives foreign funding or which is convicted of defamation twice in one year. In 2014, he approved amendments to the Law on Grants that had also limited civil society. Requirements for receiving grants are now so complicated that they have prevented a number of online outlets from continuing to operate.

The online information landscape in Azerbaijan lacks diversity, in large part due to the government’s practice of blocking independent news websites. Many outlets that have not been blocked are owned by state entities or by private figures with close ties to government leadership, and they generally produce progovernment content. The existence of these outlets is contingent upon remaining in the leadership’s good graces. For example, after presidential adviser Ali Hasanov fell into disfavor, several progovernment publications linked to him were closed down or transferred to other parties. The head of the Turan Information Agency, Mehman Aliyev, has observed that Azerbaijan’s independent media have struggled to stay afloat since the 1990s. According to IREX’s 2019 Media Stability Index, “alternative, independent broadcast TV and websites cannot directly air in Azerbaijan.

Though social media platforms such as Facebook do provide a platform for free expression—including for some marginalized or suppressed populations, such as LGBT+ people—the ability of internet users to produce and disseminate uncensored content online is undermined by persistent government pressure. Azerbaijani internet users can and do access blocked websites through VPNs.

Activists have continued to use social media to disseminate information and organize advocacy campaigns and rallies. Consequently, the government has indicated that it is interested in regulating platforms, with one lawmaker describing social media as an instrument for “moral terrorism.”

Following the outbreak of COVID-19 in Azerbaijan, ordinary users on Facebook and WhatsApp began to demand that the Ministry of Education respond to the growing crisis. Some started an online petition asking the ministry to close schools, which it did; the closures were extended through March 2021.

Facebook and YouTube were widely used during the February 2020 snap parliamentary elections to document electoral violations. As a result, Central Election Commission (CEC) head Mazahir Panahov announced that the institution would take into account all of the evidence shared on social media platforms when evaluating the results of the voting. Thanks, in part, to this evidence, results at some 100 precincts were cancelled. However, the CEC still failed to ensure that the overall balloting was fair and transparently conducted.

Connectivity issues, including the 46-day throttling of the internet and blocking of major social media platforms in 2020, hampered efforts by the political opposition to plan rallies and efforts by journalists to cover them (See A3).

(4) Violations of User Rights

The right to freedom of expression is guaranteed in the constitution, and Azerbaijan is a signatory to international agreements including the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) that protect users' rights. However, the government frequently fails to uphold freedom of expression and other fundamental rights, both offline and online.

Amendments to the Law on the Status of the Armed Forces that were approved in 2017 provided additional legal grounds for censorship, restricting journalists' ability to report on matters related to the military. At the outbreak of the conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh in September 2020, President Ilham Aliyev declared martial law, which granted the government further authority to restrict access to the internet and suspend mass media, including online media. The designation lasted from September to December 2020 (see A3 and B3).

In practice, the rights of journalists and other users to express themselves freely online are diminishing. Recent years have seen a slew of detentions, prosecutions, and in some cases very heavy sentences, for legitimate speech including criticism of the security forces, president, or other leaders; exposing poor governance or corruption; and posting information perceived by authorities as antigovernment, such as information about the COVID-19 pandemic counter to the government's preferred narrative. Authorities also used the pandemic as a pretext to persecute opponents, claiming various opposition figures who are active online had violated quarantine rules or disobeyed police. The lack of an independent judiciary leaves users facing prosecutions for online speech with few realistic avenues for recourse.

A host of problematic laws allow users to be punished for speech and other online activities that are protected under international human rights standards. These laws are often used.

Libel charges are commonly used against government critics, and the courts have confirmed that libel laws apply to social media posts. In 2013, general provisions on defamation and insult were expanded to include criminal liability for online content. Article 147.1 of the criminal code criminalizes the “dissemination, in... a publicly displayed internet information resource, of knowingly false information discrediting the honor and dignity of a person or damaging his or her reputation.” Punishments can include 1,000 to 1,500 manat (\$590 to \$880) in fines, 240 to 480 hours of community service, up to one year of corrective labor, or up to six months in jail. According to Article 147.2, falsely “accusing [someone] of having committed a serious or especially serious crime” may result in corrective labor for up to two years or imprisonment for up to three years.

Article 148 of the criminal code similarly criminalizes “deliberate humiliation of the honor and dignity of a person, expressed in an obscene manner...through a publicly displayed internet information resource.” Punishments can include fines of 300 to 1,000 manat (\$180 to \$590), 240 to 480 hours of community service, up to one year of corrective labor, or imprisonment for up to six months. A 2016 amendment to Article 148 criminalized insults disseminated online using fake “usernames, profiles, or accounts” with 1,000 to 1,500 manat (\$590 to \$880) in fines, 360 to 480 hours of community service, up to two years of corrective labor, or imprisonment for up to one year.

Also in 2016, changes to Article 323 of the criminal code introduced a maximum prison sentence of two years for defaming the president in mass media, which include social media. Defaming the president through fake “usernames, profiles, or accounts” may result in a three-year prison sentence. Falsely accusing the president of “having committed a serious or especially serious crime” online may result in a five-year prison sentence. In 2017, the fines associated with these offenses were increased.

Under the code of administrative offenses, individuals, officials, and legal entities can be fined for publishing “prohibited information.” In March 2020, the code of administrative offenses was amended such that individuals and officials can face up to one month of administrative detention for publishing “prohibited information.”

Since 2013, the code of administrative offenses has allowed courts to hold individuals in administrative detention for up to 90 days. Administrative detention, which can be imposed for offenses such as disorderly conduct, has been used to punish activists and journalists.

The SIM cards, serial numbers, and phone numbers of all mobile phones in Azerbaijan must be registered. This requirement was introduced by the Cabinet of Ministers in 2011 without parliamentary approval. Mobile operators are required to limit service to any unregistered devices.

The use of encryption services is not prohibited, and many civil society activists rely on secure messaging applications to carry out their work. This, however, does not necessarily protect them from state-sponsored hacking (see C8). While no law specifically requires users to turn over decryption keys when they are arrested or detained, authorities gain access to encrypted accounts and devices in practice through intimidation or torture.

For several years, parliament members have been proposing to introduce compulsory use of national IDs when registering with social media platforms and posting comments, but this has yet to be approved.

During the coverage period time, the throttling of the internet also prevented some users from using secure communication apps and VPNs.

State surveillance is pervasive, though the exact extent to which security agencies monitor ICT activity or track users remains unclear. The government is believed to make use of Russia's System for Operative Investigative Measures (SORM), in part because at least one Russian company involved in the manufacture of SORM-compliant interception hardware has done business with Azerbaijani authorities.

In January 2021, the government lifted the system for enforcing quarantine measures that required residents to receive permission from the police via short-message service (SMS) to leave their homes, which was originally introduced in April 2020. Failing to produce permission when asked by a police officer would result in a fine of 100 to 200 manat (\$58 to \$117) and up to one month of administrative detention. In May 2020, this system was wound down, but it was later reintroduced when the country's COVID-19 caseload began to increase.

In June 2020, the government rolled out a mandatory health care app called e-TEBIB. Test results for COVID-19 were made available exclusively through e-TEBIB. The app's user agreement stated that personal data would be retained for a month and then destroyed, but failed to specify the government institutions that can access this data and how long those institutions would store it. In July 2020, changes were made to the applications terms and agreements, which stated that personal information may be transferred to third parties only under necessary circumstances and within the existing legal framework—again failing to explicitly specify which government institution would have access to this information.

Beyond the scope of this report's coverage period, in July 2021, a sprawling investigative initiative led by Forbidden Stories, a non-profit that aims to publish journalists facing threats, concluded that the Pegasus software, produced by the Israeli cybersurveillance company NSO Group, had been used against journalists and activists in countries around the world, including Azerbaijan. Reporters with the Organized Crime and Corruption Reporting Project (OCCRP), which was among the groups working on the project, found some 250 potential targets in Azerbaijan, the majority of which were "dissidents, activists, journalists, and opposition politicians." It added that "journalists came under particular pressure, with dozens of prominent names, including OCCRP's Khadija Ismayilova, appearing on the list."

In December 2019, a report by the NGO Qurium indicated that the government may be using Find Face facial-recognition technology. In its analysis, Qurium identified an AzerTelecom server running the software.

In October 2018, Israeli newspaper *Haaretz* reported that Israel's Verint Systems had sold surveillance equipment and software to the Azerbaijani government, and local police later used it to identify the sexual orientation of users on Facebook. The timing of the transaction overlapped with an unprecedented crackdown on LGBT+ people in Azerbaijan in September 2017 and a number of seemingly random detentions and arrests.

An April 2018 report by Qurium revealed that the Azerbaijani government had purchased specialized security equipment from the Israeli company Allot Communications in 2015 for some \$3 million. The government has begun using the equipment's DPI capabilities (see B1).

In 2015, leaked documents from the Italian surveillance company Hacking Team showed that the Azerbaijani government was a client. Citizen Lab had reported in 2014 that the government was using RCS (Remote Control System) spyware sold by Hacking Team. RCS allows anyone with access to activate a targeted device's camera and microphone and to steal videos, photos, documents, contact lists, or emails. It has been used by governments around the world to spy on dissidents.

The Law on Operative-Search Activity (Article 10, Section IV) authorizes law enforcement agencies to conduct surveillance without a court order in cases where it is regarded as necessary to prevent serious crimes against individuals or especially dangerous crimes against the state. The vaguely written provision leaves the law open to abuse. It has long been believed that the State Security Service and the Ministry of Internal Affairs monitor the communications of certain individuals, especially foreigners, prominent political activists, and business figures. During the military conflict between Armenia and Azerbaijan in Nagorno-Karabakh, the State Security Service closely monitored online discussions and called into questioning those who were critical of the war. At least five activists were questioned over antiwar statements posted online (see C3).

The 2010 personal data law regulates the collection, processing, and protection of personal data—that is, an individual's name, date of birth, racial or ethnic background, religion, family, health status, and criminal record—as well as issues related to the cross-border transfer of personal data. It is not clear whether the law is enforced or respected in practice.

The Ministry of Communications requires all telecommunications companies to make their equipment and facilities available to the State Security Service. Mobile service providers are known to surrender the content of users' conversations without a court order.

In April 2020, Ali Karimli, leader of the opposition Popular Front party, began to experience a prolonged fixed and mobile internet outage, which also affected his family (see A3). The outage appeared to be a targeted, individualized disruption. Amid the outage, Karimli, his supporters, and journalists had difficulty getting in contact with his ISP and his mobile operator, Azercell. Karimli later sued these companies along with several government institutions, but a court dismissed the suit. He also sent his router to be inspected by a repair service, only to never hear from the company. Meanwhile, in an interview, member of parliament Zahid Oruc suggested that Karimli simply get a new SIM card.

During this time, Karimli's WhatsApp and Telegram accounts were also reportedly hijacked; Popular Front member Fuad Gahramanli accused Azercell of diverting Karimli's two-factor authentication codes to progovernment hackers. Azercell denied the charge.

In January 2019, the government shut down mobile internet and phone service during a political rally; later, scores of attendees were questioned by police based on location data taken from their mobile devices. Many took to social media platforms to accuse mobile service providers of disclosing the names, phone numbers, and location data of subscribers who attended the rally. When Azadliq Radio inquired about these accusations, mobile companies cited the need to comply with certain legislation. Media law expert Alasgar Mammadli noted that according to Article 39 of the Law on Communication, the service providers are obliged to provide government institutions with any requested subscriber data.

Campaigns of extralegal intimidation by authorities against perceived political opponents are common, and there are credible reports of such figures having been tortured while in state custody.

In April 2021, comedy blogger Fuad Rasulzadeh was beaten after he made a comment mocking a soldier who died during the military conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh. Rasulzadeh had also recently made satirical comments about the president.

In January 2021, Sadar Asgarov, a resident of Mingachevir city, was beaten by police over Facebook posts criticizing local government officials. The Mingachevi police arrived at his door claiming to be from the city's employment center. Once he left his house, he was beaten by three men and taken to the police station in a van. At the police station, the deputy police chief slapped him, confiscated his phone, and deleted his social media platforms. He was also forced to make an apology, which the police filmed; eventually he was let go after being fined.

In November 2020, Latif Mammadov was questioned and threatened as a result of his antiwar activism. The officers grabbed Mammadov by the collar and threatened to kill his parents unless he stopped his online activism.

In October 2020, a group of peace activists were targeted online by a Facebook page called Pinochet Airlines over their criticism of the ongoing military action in Nagorno-Karabakh. The page, which was eventually taken down by Facebook, shared pictures of the activists and called for public action against them. On Twitter, some users called for the execution of "no war" activists.

During the coverage period, a number of women also experienced harassment or had personal photos of them leaked on the internet, including a spate of attacks around International Women's Day. In March 2021, Narmin Sharmarzadeh, a prominent activist who had previously been arrested, had her account hacked and the attackers posted pornographic videos. She speculated that the attackers might have been trying to delete a Facebook event she was hosting in support of International Women's Day. Though the videos were ultimately deleted from Facebook, they were shared on Telegram as well. In the same month, an intimate video of Gunel Hasanli, the daughter of opposition figure Jamil Hasanli, was released. Likewise, the sister of blogger Mahammad Mirzali also had an intimate video leaked online in March, which she said pushed her to the brink of suicide. In June 2020, Amina Rustamzade, the wife of former political prisoner Ilkin Rustamzade, attempted suicide after being harassed in April 2020 by pseudonymous social media users who shared revealing photos of her on Facebook and Instagram without her consent. Before she attempted suicide, Rustamzade had received a message from a Facebook user who threatened that "what happened earlier will happen again."

The government also uses travel bans to stymie prominent critics, and authorities pressure lawyers who represent defendants in freedom-of-expression cases.

In order to suppress dissidents in exile, the government regularly intimidates dissidents' relatives who remain in Azerbaijan.

Opposition news websites and activists continued to be targeted by cyberattacks, ranging from distributed denial of services (DDoS) attacks to spear-phishing attempts that are believed to be state-sponsored.

In February and March 2021, a number of women activists had their accounts hacked. In February, personal information obtained from hacked accounts belonging to Gulnara Mehdiyeva, one of the founders of the feminist movement in Azerbaijan, were leaked to discredit her ahead of International Women's Day 2021. In March 2021, Narmin Sharmarzadeh, also had her Facebook account hacked (see C7). Azerbaijan Internet Watch traced an IP address linked to these attacks to the Ministry of Interior and the MTCHT. Additionally, Azerbaijan Internet Watch speculated that the telecommunications companies could have been complicit because many of those who experienced hacks had set up two-factor authentication, but did not receive SMS messages when their accounts were breached. In March 2020, ahead of International Women's Day, members of a feminist movement and LGBT+ rights activists, including Mehdiyeva, were targeted in the aftermath of an unsanctioned rally organized to mark the day. Her social media accounts, email, and Telegram app were hacked. Additionally, the attacker removed her from several women's rights-oriented Facebook pages she was administering. The Facebook groups were also compromised, suspended, or deactivated. Minority Magazine, Azerbaijan's first digital magazine focusing on LGBT+ rights, and Nefes LGBT Azerbaijan Alliance were also targeted. Both groups lost years' worth of content as a result.

In September 2020, a Facebook page affiliated with Bastinfo.com, an opposition online news platform, was hacked. The page lost approximately 5,000 followers and content shared since 2017.

In September 2020, Rustam Ismayilbeyli, an activist advocating for fair education in Azerbaijan, was blackmailed online. Ismayilbeyli was arrested earlier in July for protesting outside the Ministry of Education and sentenced to 15 days of administrative detention. His social media accounts, email, and cloud were compromised during his time in detention. He also received two messages via Facebook from accounts posing as a State Security Service employee. The message stated unless he cooperated with the authorities, they would leak personal information and intimate pictures of him and his girlfriend. The same month, Ismayilbeyli reported an attempted break-in to his Telegram account, but it was not compromised.

In June 2020, numerous figures in Azerbaijani civil society were targeted in an apparently coordinated digital attack. Targets included human rights lawyer Intigam Aliyev, the opposition group D18, freelance journalist Aysel Umudova, student activist Rustam Ismayilbeyli, and freelance journalist Fatima Movlamli, all of whom said their Facebook pages had been attacked. In September 2020, Nigar Hezi, an opposition activist, also experienced a break-in attempt into her Facebook profile.

In June 2020, Berlin-based Meydan TV had its social media account targeted, ultimately losing two years' worth of content on Facebook and two months' worth of content on Instagram. In the same month, online news outlet Arqument.az had its Facebook page hacked. As a result, the page lost 12,000 followers, and all its posts on the platform through March 2020 were removed.

For three days in May 2020, the website of Turan News Agency was subject to DDoS attacks.

In May 2020, four videos from a private Zoom call among members of the opposition National Council were leaked online. In each of the videos, various members of the National Council criticized opposition groups and voiced antigay insults about one US-based Azerbaijani journalist. The call's participants described the leaks as a cybercrime, alluding to the use of

NSO Group's Pegasus software, and demanding a full investigation. Azerbaijani officials dismissed the allegations.

In January 2020, perpetrators targeted Azerbaijani civil society in a coordinated phishing attack. At the time, Qurium traced the malware to the same entity behind a DDoS attack on the online news website Criminal.az. At least two online news websites, Azadliq and HamamTimes, were targeted with WeTransfer links. On January 11, 2020, a larger group of civil society figures received WeTransfer links purportedly from Roberto Fasino, a Council of Europe official, containing malware. The actor behind these phishing attempts appeared to be using Facebook as a vector for infecting targets.

Columbia

In order to analyze the digital situation in Columbia, this section will be comprised of two smaller subsections,. The two stages describes are: (1) Overview and (2) Violations of User Rights

(1) Overview

Internet freedom in Colombia declined for the fourth consecutive year. People used digital tools to mobilize during protests against police brutality in September 2020, as well as during nationwide protests that were sparked by proposed tax reforms in April 2021. Police responded to the mobilization with deadly force, arbitrary detentions of online media personnel, and seizures of electronic devices in certain instances. Moreover, during the coverage period, at least one service provider blocked two websites, and several journalists were targeted with criminal defamation inquiries. Despite these challenges, internet access continued to expand, fixed broadband speeds have improved, and government initiatives have reduced the digital divide.

Colombia is among the longest-standing democracies in Latin America, but one with a history of widespread violence and serious human rights abuses. Public institutions have demonstrated the capacity to check executive power and enforce the rule of law, and violence declined as the government and the country's main left-wing guerrilla group moved toward a peace accord signed in 2016. Nonetheless, Colombia still faces enormous challenges in consolidating peace and guaranteeing political rights and civil liberties outside of major urban areas.

(2) Violations of User Rights

Colombia's constitution includes protections for free expression, though judges sometimes rule against these rights through disproportionate orders to restrict content. Article 20 of the constitution guarantees freedom of information and expression and prohibits prior restraint. Article 73 further provides for the protection of "the liberty and professional independence" of "journalistic activity." Although there are no specific provisions protecting freedom of expression online, according to the Constitutional Court, online journalists and bloggers have the same liberties and protections as print or broadcast journalists.

The judiciary consistently exhibits independence. However, judges sometimes rule against free expression, frequently ordering content to be restricted based on an "acción de tutela" (see B3).

Colombia maintains criminal penalties for defamation. According to the Colombian penal code, individuals accused of making “dishonourable accusations” can face up to four-and-a-half years in jail, while individuals accused of libel can face up to six years in jail. Sanctions may be heightened when the crime is committed through the use of “social mediums of communication or of other collective divulgence.” Whoever “publishes, reproduces, or repeats” dishonourable accusations or libel may also be subject to the same punishment.

According to the Center for Studies on Freedom of Expression and Access to Information at Palermo University, 36 percent of laws passed between 1998 and 2020 that restrict freedom of speech fail to meet legality, necessity, and proportionality standards.

Though a number of bills have been proposed in recent years with potential to restrict online expression, including by increasing government regulation of social networks or prohibiting broadly defined content, none had passed by the end of the coverage period. Congress did, however, approve a new electoral code in December 2020 that includes provisions that could threaten free speech, which is currently awaiting review by the Constitutional Court. Multiple free expression and digital rights organizations jointly filed an intervention with the Constitutional Court against the new code, arguing that it establishes disproportionate and ambiguous restrictions on citizen’s political expression over social media. For example, the code classifies “any expression that denigrates women in exercise of their political functions” as gender-based political violence and broadly prohibits such content, providing a vague definition that could be used to censor legitimate criticism.

Prosecution and imprisonment for online activities is quite rare in Colombia, though brief detentions have become more common amidst recent political and social unrest. Writers, commentators, and bloggers are not systematically subject to imprisonment or fines for posting material on the internet. Criminal defamation suits pose a legitimate threat to journalists.

Brief prison sentences have been handed to journalists in connection to their online activities in the past, though they do not always serve all (or any) of their sentences. In March and October 2020, respectively, journalists Edison Lucio Torres and Gustavo Rugeles were handed fines and brief prison sentences after being sanctioned for not complying with orders to take down articles from their respective news sites that alleged corruption by a religious leader and a public servant. However, only Lucio Torres ended up serving his ten-day sentence. Previously, in August 2018, Juvenal Bolívar, a journalist at news outlet *Corillos*, and Sofía Ortiz Delgado, a former staff member there, each served a 10-day sentence after Bolívar refused to comply with a ruling ordering him to withdraw an investigation into a city official from his website, after a process plagued by procedural irregularities.

Digital media personnel covering protests also risk arbitrary detention by authorities. In June 2020, three contributors to *ab zurdo*, a photography account on Instagram, were detained and held overnight while covering a demonstration against the government’s COVID-19 response. The three social media users had identified themselves as press, and were released after receiving a fine for violating the city’s lockdown orders, despite regulation allowing reporters to go outside during the lockdown. Four journalists from the digital medium *La Otra Verdad* were also detained for seven hours while covering protests in September 2020, after identifying themselves as press to police.

Criminal defamation suits were filed against journalists in retaliation for their online reporting during the reporting period. In September 2020, two freelance journalists for the online news

magazine *Volcánicas* were ordered by the attorney general's office to appear for questioning for a criminal defamation complaint that had been filed against them in July of that year. The complainant, screenwriter and director *Ciro Guerra Picón*, filed the case in response to an article the journalists published in June 2020 reporting on at least eight separate cases accusing *Picón* of sexual harassment. In May 2021, a court ordered the journalists to add additional context and details to their published testimonies. Separately, in April 2021, the attorney general's office notified investigative journalist *Jeremy McDermott* of a criminal defamation suit filed against him by Colombia businessman *Guillermo Acevedo*. The lawsuit is in response to a series published on *McDermott's* investigative site, *InSight Crime*, that alleged that the complainant used to be a drug trafficker and paramilitary leader. *Acevedo* was arrested in June 2021 on charges of illicit enrichment, criminal conspiracy, and money laundering.

A nascent criminal case with significant implications for journalists who expose media censorship also began during the coverage period. In October 2020, the attorney general's office announced it would file criminal charges against former public TV station manager, *Diana Díaz*, due to a complaint filed against her by her former supervisor the year before. *Díaz* had leaked audio clips to the Foundation for Press Freedom (FLIP) in which her supervisor, *Francisco Pablo Bieri*, suggested cancelling a program after its host had criticized a proposed telecommunications law. There were no updates to the case as of the end of the coverage period.

Intercepting personal communications in Colombia is authorized only for criminal investigation purposes and legally requires a judicial order. Colombian law allows intelligence agencies to monitor devices that use the electromagnetic spectrum to transmit wireless communication without a judicial order.

Episodes of extralegal surveillance carried out by intelligence agencies, the army, and the police against journalists, activists, and opposition leaders have constituted an ongoing scandal in Colombia for over ten years. Some steps have been taken in recent years to punish perpetrators, including with the arrests of former heads of illegal wiretapping and interception networks. The Inter-American Commission on Human (IACHR) confirmed in October 2020, however, that impunity persists for those conducting illegal surveillance.

Two investigations published by the magazine *Semana* in January and May 2020 revealed the processes and equipment used in illegal military surveillance. The January report exposed the use of sophisticated technology and open-source intelligence—including International Mobile Subscriber Identity (IMSI) catcher equipment, a malware system called *Invisible Man*, and the artificial intelligence tool *Voyager*—to spy on politicians, magistrates, generals, social leaders, activists, and journalists in 2019. The military used technology originally provided by the United States to address drug trafficking and the fight against guerrillas, compiling files on each target that included excerpts of social media conversations, photographs, videos, contacts, and maps tracing their movements. The May report noted that military intelligence targeted 130 people for surveillance in 2019, including 30 journalists from prominent outlets, human rights defenders, and the regional head of Human Rights Watch (HRW).

Social media monitoring also threatens the continued activities of journalists and activists. In August 2020, a national observatory revealed that the mayor of Medellín, *Daniel Quintero*, had used public resources to hire a firm to monitor the social media profiles of journalists, social leaders, politicians, and regular citizens who were critical of his administration in 2020.

In 2015, documents leaked from the technology company Hacking Team, which is known to provide spyware to governments, suggested that the Colombian government had contracts with the company. Police would only acknowledge having contractual ties with a Colombian company called Robotec, which distributes Hacking Team's services, though the leaked documents indicate that the national police contacted Hacking Team directly to activate spyware. Another leaked email suggested that the US Drug Enforcement Agency (DEA) may have been conducting surveillance in Colombia through spyware and dragnet internet surveillance.

Also in 2015, Privacy International found that the Bogotá police bought technology from the companies NICE (sold to Elbit Systems the same year) and Verint that could intercept phone calls in order to monitor government opponents. According to a 2018 investigation by Israeli newspaper *Haaretz*, Colombia has continued to purchase technology from Verint.

While some constitutional and legal protections regulate the government's use of data, service providers in Colombia are obligated to share data with the intelligence community with limited judicial review; providers are also obligated to capture and store user data for use in criminal investigations.

Service providers are required to collaborate with intelligence agencies by providing access, when feasible, to the communications history, location data, or technical data of any specific user without a warrant; intelligence agencies conducting an authorized operation only need to request the data. However, Colombian intelligence and counterintelligence agencies are also subject to Statutory Law 1621 of 2013, which binds agencies to respect "rights to honor, good name, personal and family privacy, and due process." Article 4 restricts the discriminatory use of intelligence data, including on the basis of gender, race, or origin (see C5).

Service providers are also obliged to retain subscriber data for the purposes of criminal investigations and intelligence activities for a period of five years. An additional threat to user privacy comes in the form of Article 2 of Decree 1704 (2012), which requires that ISPs create access points that capture communications traffic on their networks for criminal investigation purposes—which can be used under the prosecutor general's authorization. A service provider that does not comply with these obligations faces fines and could lose its operating license.

In March 2020, the Superintendence of Industry and Commerce (SIC), a consumer protection agency that operates under the purview of Colombia's trade ministry, released a circular that authorized telecommunications firms to share user data with public authorities as part of the country's COVID-19 response. While public entities are obliged to secure data and respect its confidentiality, the decision opens users to risks including discrimination, undue surveillance, invasion of privacy, and the revelation of journalistic sources. The circular does not specify what data should be collected and imposes no time limit.

Online outlets and journalists have been targeted by cyberattacks, and in 2020, FLIP recorded 10 cyberattacks against websites belonging to media outlets.

Journalists have recently been victims of hacking attempts. In April 2021, Diana Calderón announced that her WhatsApp account had been hacked and was now part of a hacking chain, in which her contacts would receive requests for a code from her account that would allow the hackers full access to their own accounts, if provided. Calderón is the director of a radio show and regularly writes articles for *El País* that are published online. The hack also targeted high-level politicians and two other Colombian journalists.

Outlets themselves are also among the victims of cyberattacks. In March 2020, before the coverage period, online news outlet La Oreja Roja published an article discussing deceased drug trafficker José Guillermo “Añe” Hernández’s suspected involvement in a vote-buying campaign during the 2018 presidential election. The website was made inaccessible the weekend after the article was published.

Government institutions also face cyberattacks, including in retaliation for the state’s crackdown on protesters during the coverage period. This was the justification provided by Anonymous in April 2021 when the group claimed to have used distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks, which aim to crash websites by bombarding their host servers with information requests, to take down the official pages of the presidency and the senate. They also claimed to have leaked the personal information of members of the army through cyberattacks.

Sri Lanka

In order to analyze the digital situation in Sri Lanka, this section will be comprised of three smaller subsections,. The four stages describes are: (1) Overview (2) Limits on Content and (3) Violations of User Rights

(1) Overview

Internet freedom remained constrained in Sri Lanka. Although the government refrained from blocking social media or communications platforms in 2020 and 2021, which enabled Sri Lankans to engage in digital activism around a broad range of issues, the online space for free expression continued to shrink. Journalists and activists reported increased intimidation and harassment, contributing to self-censorship and a more fearful climate. Separately, arrests for online activity related to COVID-19 and environmental issues increased and the police arrested a few individuals without a warrant for their online speech. An online news site became the target of distributed-denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks, while government websites, including the prime minister’s website, were hacked.

Sri Lanka experienced improvements in political rights and civil liberties after the 2015 election of President Maithripala Sirisena, which ended the more repressive rule of Mahinda Rajapaksa. However, the Sirisena administration was slow to implement transitional justice mechanisms needed to address the aftermath of a 26-year civil war between government forces and ethnic Tamil rebels, who were defeated in 2009. Gotabaya Rajapaksa’s election as president in

November 2019 and the Sri Lanka Podujana Peramuna's victory in the August 2020 parliamentary polls have emboldened the Rajapaksa family, which has taken steps to empower the executive and roll back accountability mechanisms for civil war-era rights violations.

(2) Limits on Content

The government does not systematically block or filter websites and other forms of online content, although a few independent websites and other sites are blocked. Authorities have previously blocked social media and communications platforms.

SLT's unlimited data packages, which became available in April 2021, blocks torrents, P2P applications, and Telegram under their terms and conditions (see C4).

Lankaenews remained blocked on Dialog connections during the coverage period, although it was accessible on SLT connections. The website was reportedly first blocked for publishing stories critical of then president Sirisena.

During the coverage period, tests from the internet censorship organization OONI revealed signs of HTTP blocking for several websites. Sankanthi24.com, a Tamil news site, first showed signs of being blocked in June 2020 and continued to show signs as of June 2021 on Dialog and SLT connections, though it was accessible outside the country. Adult dating site adultfriendfinder.com also showed signs of HTTP blocking on Dialog connections starting from September 2020 to June 2021, though it was accessible on SLT. The official website of the US Navy's Sea, Air, and Land (SEAL) teams showed signs of TCP/IP blocking from June 2020 to June 2021 on both Dialog and SLT connections, but remained accessible outside the country. US-based news site Jezebel appeared to have been affected by domain name system (DNS) tampering on Dialog connections from September 2020 to June 2021.

Separately, the government has blocked websites that address health and intimate issues. Teen health, relationship, and sexuality site teenhealthfx.com, which showed signs of DNS tampering in the previous coverage period, is now accessible on both Dialog and SLT connections. The government previously blocked social media and communication platforms three times in April and May 2019, in the aftermath of the Easter Sunday attacks, and once for over a week in March 2018 in response to violence in Kandy (see A3). Authorities claimed the restrictions were necessary to stop the spread of disinformation and hateful content, as well as limit sectarian violence during the politically tense weeks and months following the attacks. The restrictions, however, prevented access to independent news sources and limited users' ability to contact those in areas affected by the crisis.

In recent years, the Sri Lankan government has considered instituting a legal framework to curb online speech it considers discriminatory along with speech it considers misleading. The government also issued takedown requests during the reporting period.

Between July and December 2020, Facebook temporarily restricted access to 1,643 items to adhere to election guidelines related to that August's parliamentary polls.

Election guidelines restrict candidates and supporters from campaigning in the two days before polling. Facebook also restricted access to one piece of content for violating privacy laws. In the same period, Google received 39 removal requests, including 9 requests over accusations of defamation, 8 over privacy or security concerns, 7 over nudity or adult content, 3 over harassment, 3 involving criticism of the government, and 3 involving religious content. Google also received 1 request each in categories of copyright, electoral, hate speech, impersonation, violence, and “other.” One request came from the Criminal Investigations Department (CID) about two Blogger posts that were allegedly defaming a business. Google, however, did not comply with this request. Twitter reported one legal demand to remove content between January and June 2020, to which it did not comply.

After the presidential election in November 2019, the Defense Ministry announced that a new mechanism would be introduced to immediately remove social media posts that were defamatory or spread ethnic– or religious-based hatred. In November 2020, the government again announced its intention to introduce a regulatory framework based on Singapore's Protection from Online Falsehoods and Manipulation Act, aimed at curbing hate speech and misinformation. In April 2021, the cabinet was granted approval to draft laws to curb false and misleading online posts. In December 2020, the government announced its intention to register foreign digital operators, although there have been no further updates on this effort.

There is a lack of transparency around restrictions of online content, but a 2017 right to information (RTI) request revealed some of the government's blocking procedures. The government's response revealed that blocking orders can originate from the Mass Media Ministry and the Presidential Secretariat for a number of reasons, including “publishing false information” and “damaging the president's reputation. Orders are then sent to the TRCSL, which instructs ISPs to block the content. The TRCSL denied part of the RTI request on national security grounds, and an appeal of the case was heard before the RTI Commission in the spring of 2018. There are no records of ISPs challenging the TRCSL's blocking orders at the commission itself or through the court.

It is not clear if the TRCSL can impose financial or legal penalties on telecommunications companies that do not comply with blocking orders, since the conditions of such orders are unknown to the public. Under the Telecommunications Act, ISPs are licensed by the Telecommunications Ministry, but the TRCSL can make recommendations on whether a license should be granted. The ministry can impose conditions on a license, requiring the provider to address any matter considered “requisite or expedient to achieving” TRCSL objectives.

There is no independent body regulating content, which leaves limited avenues for appeal (see A5). Content providers have filed fundamental rights applications with the Supreme Court to challenge blocking orders, but under former president Mahinda Rajapaksa, the lack of public trust in the politicized judiciary and fear of retaliatory measures presented significant obstacles for would-be petitioners.

Following the Easter Sunday attacks, the government claimed it would introduce new social media regulations. In December 2020, the government further explained it was considering introducing registration requirements for foreign digital operators. No concrete legislation, however, had been passed as of June 2021.

There have been increasing efforts from domestic actors—including government officials, civil society, and fact checkers—to work with international technology companies. For example, in March 2020, Facebook committed to removing false claims or conspiracy theories flagged by global and local health authorities related to COVID-19. Also in March, it was reported that the Elections Commission (EC) would be working with officials from Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube to monitor content during the August polls and to ensure the platforms would not be misused for content like hate speech. A report from youth group Hashtag Generation noted that Facebook did remove several instances of election-related hate speech, false news, and targeted harassment reported to them by the EC during the elections.

Previously, during the 2019 presidential elections, Facebook committed to removing content that would deter people from voting. Separately, ahead of the vote, the EC warned that it would take legal action against electronic and online media organizations spreading false content or hate speech.

Facebook's content-removal policies generated controversy in the aftermath of communal violence in March 2018. Facebook was criticized for failing to remove hateful Sinhala-language content that analysts argued encouraged anti-Muslim violence. In June 2018, Facebook representatives met with local civil society activists and committed to improve their language capabilities to better moderate content. In March 2020, critics pointed out that, as moderators transitioned to working from home, posts promoting misinformation on Facebook continued to be shared more than credible news, despite the platform pledging to remove some types of misleading content. In May 2020, Facebook apologized for its role in the communal violence targeting Muslims in 2018, and released a human rights impact assessment report, which highlighted that the automated detection of hate speech in Sinhala and reporting channels within Facebook Messenger had been improved with added policy and language expertise. The report made several recommendations on accountability, changes to platform architecture and grievance mechanisms, and improving community standards. Some recommendations drew mixed reactions from members of civil society, who noted shortfalls in terms of guidance in local languages for Sri Lankan users.

Civil society organizations previously criticized a January 2019 meeting between senior Facebook employees and government officials including then-president Sirisena, former president Mahinda Rajapaksa, and then prime minister Ranil Wickremesinghe. The meeting was ostensibly about disinformation, although activists were concerned that the participants focused on content moderation and censorship.

While self-censorship by journalists declined under the former Sirisena administration, journalists have since proceeded with caution when reporting on subjects that are considered sensitive.

In February 2021, UN High Commissioner for Human Rights Michelle Bachelet raised concerns that the surveillance and harassment reported by over 40 civil society organizations was having a “chilling [effect on] civic and democratic space and leading to self-censorship.” Following the November 2019 election of President Gotabaya Rajapaksa, journalists and activists reported an increase in self-censorship around political issues. In previous years, journalists have noted a tendency to self-censor when covering the president and the first family. Harassment and intimidation leveled against journalists may also contribute to self-censorship (see C7).

Gihan Nicholas—who works for the news site NewsHub, which had criticized the Rajapaksas ahead of the election—reported that after the vote, “The mood is one of self-censorship. [Journalists are] holding back.” Members of Tamil and Sinhala media outlets have reportedly faced increasing pressure from officials and are increasingly self-censoring. Journalists from the Tamil daily *Thinakkural* and the English-language *Daily Express* said they were hesitant to criticize the Rajapaksas; *Thinakkural* journalists reportedly considered rights violations, the army, corruption, missing people, and land appropriation to be “sensitive” topics. The Committee to Protect Journalists (CPJ) also noted that at least two journalists went into exile following the presidential election. Separately, a few prominent anonymous Twitter accounts sharing satirical or other forms of political speech, notably on Tamil issues or focused on the north of the country, closed their accounts due to security concerns.

Under former president Sirisena, self-censorship by journalists online appeared to be decreasing, in part due to the government’s stated commitment to press freedom. Both traditional and online media outlets expressed a diversity of political viewpoints, including criticism of the government.

The spread of disinformation and misinformation has been a growing concern in recent years. A 2020 report from the Oxford Internet Institute identified Sri Lanka as having permanent cybertroop teams that manipulated information on Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube on behalf of politicians and political parties. The report found evidence that Sri Lankan teams work to support preferred messaging, attack the opposition, create division, and suppress critical content.

Disinformation increased in the lead-up to and during the August 2020 elections, including some originating from political parties and candidates. For example, one candidate implied that the elections commissioner was attempting to limit voter turnout in an interview shared on Facebook. Several political candidates also questioned the integrity of the vote-counting process on social media.

Some government regulations threaten the economic viability of online publishers and start-up platforms. In late 2019, the government issued new guidelines for media

accreditation that include websites and online journalists covering news and current events. Beginning in 2020, a special committee appointed by the director general of government information would issue media cards, and websites were required to register with the Mass Media Ministry. Websites that have not registered do not receive media accreditation, which restricts them from covering certain events and hinders their field reporting. The purported purpose of the guidelines is to ensure better media practices.

The government also maintained news site registration requirements introduced by previous administrations. During Mahinda Rajapaksa's presidency, the Mass Media Ministry directed all news sites to register for a fee of 25,000 rupees (\$130), with an annual renewal fee of 10,000 rupees (\$53).

(3) Violation of User Rights

Although internet access is not guaranteed as a fundamental right in legislation, Article 14 (1)(a) of the constitution protects freedom of expression, subject to restrictions related to the protection of national security, public order, racial and religious harmony, and morality. There are no specific constitutional provisions guaranteeing freedom of expression online. In 2019, the government moved to restrict free expression and press freedom with the implementation of emergency regulations and the approval of new amendments targeting false information online (see C2).

In January 2021, the cabinet approved a proposal to amend the 1970s-era Press Council Law. The amendments would restructure the Press Council to regulate new outlets and electronic media as it already does in the print sector. Civil society has expressed worries that the amendments would expand the government's control over online media and online speech.

Following the Easter Sunday attacks in April 2019, the government declared a state of emergency and passed emergency regulations. The regulations created a new competent authority appointed by the president. This authority could limit the publication of certain materials, including online materials, which included content deemed threatening to national security or disruptive to public order or the provision of essential services. The authority required that certain types of content be reviewed before being published. The regulations also prohibited the spread of false statements that could cause public disorder or alarm. Under the regulations, people could appeal decisions made by the competent authority to new advisory committees. The state of emergency was lifted in August 2019.

Since the passage of the Right to Information Act in 2017, citizens have submitted thousands of RTI applications on issues ranging from legislation on the rights of people with disabilities to the blocking of websites (see B3).

A culture of impunity, circumvention of the judicial process through arbitrary action, and a lack of adequate protection for individuals and their privacy compounded the poor

enforcement of freedom-of-expression guarantees under former president Mahinda Rajapaksa's government. These issues persisted into former president Sirisena's government and continue under the current administration.

Several vaguely defined, overly broad laws can be abused to prosecute users and restrict online expression.

In June 2019, the cabinet approved vague amendments to the criminal and penal codes that criminalize the spread of "false news" affecting "communal harmony" or "state security." These terms are left undefined in the amendments, leaving them open to abuse. If passed, an offense can be punished with a fine of more than one million rupees (\$53,500), and a maximum prison sentence of five years. However, as of June 2021, the amendments have not been passed by Parliament. In April 2021, the government announced it was again considering penal-code amendments to criminalize false news, with news reports saying the government had approved concept papers in May 2021. The police recently cited a number of existing laws which could be used to arrest people for spreading misinformation, including sections of the penal code, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) Act, the Computer Crime Act, the PTA, and sections of the Obscene Publications Act.

The government has drafted a Cyber Security Act, which is expected to tackle cybercrime, the nonconsensual dissemination of intimate images, and hacking and intellectual property theft. A proposed draft of the bill was posted online in May 2019. The IT industry criticized the lack of transparency in the process and the broad definitions contained in the draft bill. Some civil society representatives also criticized the limited time for feedback and noted that Sinhala and Tamil translations were not available for consultations. Others pointed out that broad definitions for terms like "critical information infrastructure" and "cyber security incidents" could allow for the extension of government control over private institutions, could extend criminality to "actions that are otherwise acceptable but politically inconvenient," and could have a chilling effect on privacy and freedom of expression. The final draft is not yet publicly available as of June 2021, though it was reported that the bill would be finalized by the end of the year.

Publishing official secrets, information about Parliament that may undermine its work, or "malicious" content that incites violence or disharmony can result in criminal charges. Then government information director general Sudarshana Gunawardana stated in March 2018 that incitement to violence, including on social media, is contrary to Article 28 of the constitution and Section 100 of the penal code, as well as Section 3 of the ICCPR, to which Sri Lanka is a party.

In February 2020, the foreign minister told the United Nations that the government would review and amend the PTA rather than pass the draft Counter Terrorism Act proposed by the previous government. The PTA has been previously used to crack down on critical online content, including speech from journalists. The government continues to use the PTA to detain writers, lawyers, and activists (see C3).

Authorities have increasingly manipulated the ICCPR Act, which enshrines the ICCPR in Sri Lankan domestic law, to criminalize online speech (see C3). Section 3(1), for example, prohibits national, racial, and religious hatred if it incites discrimination, hostility, and violence. Those charged under the act can only be granted bail by a high court.

State surveillance of online activities undermines users' right to privacy. The National Action Plan for the Protection and Promotion of Human Rights 2017–21 contains the objective of ensuring the constitutional recognition of the right to privacy, but in practice, this right is frequently not respected. In March 2021, an anonymous Twitter user wrote that the Defense Ministry had activated the Pegasus spyware suite with the cooperation of Dialog Axiata and Mobitel. An opposition parliamentarian also stated that the government had obtained Pegasus. Dialog, however, claimed the allegations were false.

In May 2021, the Health Ministry and the ICTA announced the launch of a digital vaccination ID, which would allow people to schedule COVID-19 vaccination and appointments and receive internationally valid vaccination certificates. The sign-up process, which is not live as of June 2021, appears to ask for health data to receive appointments and digital IDs. In February 2021, the State Ministry of Primary Healthcare, Epidemics, and COVID Disease Control launched a website for individuals to register for the COVID-19 vaccination program. The website collected personal details including names, addresses, mobile numbers, and email addresses as well as health data. The data privacy statement did not detail how collected data would be used. An estimated 50,000 people registered on the site as of February 2021; the site was subsequently taken down.

The use of mobile apps and tracking tools amid COVID-19 raised privacy concerns (see C6). A government-developed app, Rakemu Api, allows users to report their health status if they have come into contact with a COVID-19 patient or returned from overseas in the past two weeks. There was a lack of transparency about who has access to collected data, how data can be used, how information is stored, and how long information is stored. The ICTA-developed Stay Safe app also traces those who have tested positive for COVID-19 and close associates. Several restaurants and hotels now offer the option of logging into Stay Safe for contact-tracing purposes. In an April 2020 interview, the defense minister disclosed that military intelligence was receiving mobile-phone contacts of patients from service providers. He called the information an important national security tool, as it was used to track the contacts of patients as well as those who did not comply with quarantine.

Registration for a media briefing for social media users by the government-led National Development Media Centre required details like NIC numbers, even for users attending the briefings online.

Following the Easter Sunday attacks, the government indicated its intention to ramp up monitoring and surveillance. During the coverage period, while speaking about the

arrest of individuals for posts which allegedly referenced or promoted the LTTE propaganda (see C3), a government official said that the CID and TID deploy teams that monitor the internet and social media platforms. In May 2019, the then prime minister announced a plan to implement a Centralized and Integrated Population Information System (CIPIS) to track individuals engaged in terrorism, money laundering, and financial crimes. In August 2019, police announced that they were creating an integrated database and facial recognition system to “identify criminals” with SLT and other parties.

In March 2021, it was announced that the Environmental Ministry had established a special unit of 323 officers to monitor posts on social media related to environmental destruction.

During a visit to China in May 2019, then president Sirisena asked Chinese president Xi Jinping to share surveillance technology with Sri Lanka, citing the challenges of surveilling encrypted platforms. President Xi reportedly agreed to meet Sirisena’s request. There has been no update on the practical outcome of this meeting.

The introduction of the electronic identity card (e-NIC) project has also raised surveillance concerns. The project includes a central database storing wide-ranging information and biometrics with “family tree” data. Activists warn that this data could be used to target political opponents and is vulnerable to hacking. President Rajapaksa has asked that the project be expedited. There was little opposition to the project when it was first introduced, presumably because the government justified it as a needed improvement to government service-delivery operations.

Extrajudicial surveillance of personal communications is prohibited under the Telecommunications Act. However, communications can be intercepted on the order of a minister or a court, or in connection with a criminal investigation.

State agencies reportedly possess some technologies that could facilitate surveillance. In March 2019, then president Sirisena requested approval for the government to purchase 7.11 trillion rupees (\$38.9 million) worth of surveillance technology from an unnamed Israeli company. Bypassing the normal procedures for purchasing such technology, Sirisena claimed the request—which was purportedly related to tackling drug trafficking—was urgent and must be kept secret.

In 2015, leaked documents indicated that Milan-based HackingTeam was approached by several state security agencies seeking to acquire the company’s digital surveillance technologies. The leaks revealed that in 2014, the Defense Ministry was planning to develop an electronic surveillance and tracking system with the help of a local university. While no equipment purchases were confirmed in the leaked documents, the papers did include a 2013 email exchange between a HackingTeam employee and an individual claiming to represent Sri Lankan intelligence agencies, which described confidential acquisitions of “interception technologies” the individual had previously brokered. Digital activists in Sri Lanka believe that Chinese companies ZTE and

Huawei, which collaborated with Mahinda Rajapaksa's government in the development and maintenance of the Sri Lankan ICT infrastructure, may have inserted backdoor espionage and surveillance capabilities into the technology.

Government and business websites are vulnerable to hacking and other cyberattacks. While the problem is not historically widespread in Sri Lanka, notable attacks on government websites and other websites were recorded during the coverage period. Cyberattacks occasionally targeted government critics, such as the TamilNet news site, under former president Mahinda Rajapaksa.

In April 2021, the Colombo Gazette's news site was subject to a DDoS attack. The motivations of the attack were unclear. The editor speculated that the site was targeted by China because the botnet which launched the attack appeared to have originated from China and Hong Kong. However, because the attackers used CloudFlare technology, a subsequent IP trace was redirected to the closest CloudFlare server, which was in China; other experts, therefore, did not support the claim that China launched the attack.

In February 2021, shortly after Independence Day, some users accessing Google.lk were redirected to another site which highlighted minority rights issues. The TRCSL called the incident a "malicious redirection" and said it was working with the Sri Lankan domain registry to resolve the issue. It was later revealed that the domain registry's usernames and passwords had been leaked on the dark web, and that the credentials had been used on multiple sites since 2012, opening up the potential for future attacks. The registry reported that several government agency websites were being redirected. In a notice on its site, the registry acknowledged security shortcomings and noted they had since updated their systems to remove vulnerabilities.

In May 2021, recognized as the anniversary of the end of the civil war, several websites were hacked by the Tamil Eelam Cyber Force. The Health Ministry, Energy Ministry, the Sri Lankan embassy in China, and the Rajarata University websites were affected. The prime minister's website was hacked in June 2021, with the website redirecting to a site dedicated to the cryptocurrency Bitcoin.

In June 2020, several journalists' WhatsApp accounts were targeted by SIM-swapping attacks, which occur when a hacker convinces a service provider to switch a phone number to a new device that is under their control. This allows the hacker to access the targeted person's two-factor authentication. Those affected included members of the Groundviews WhatsApp group, which was subsequently shut down, and potentially other journalist WhatsApp groups. In May 2021, the TRCSL issued a notice that SIM-swapping attacks continued to occur on WhatsApp.

The draft Cyber Security Act, which would establish a Cyber Security Agency and implement the National Cyber Security Strategy of Sri Lanka, is expected to include provisions for protection against hacking (see C2).

Hackers frequently attack government and business websites, and in 2016 one technology company placed Sri Lanka among the top 10 countries in the Asia-Pacific region facing increased threats to cybersecurity. In May 2019, several local websites, such as that of the Kuwaiti embassy in Colombo, were defaced by unknown hackers.

United States of America

In order to analyze the digital situation in USA, this section will be comprised of two smaller subsections,. The four stages describes are: (1) Overview and (2) Violations of User Rights

(1) Overview

For the fifth year in a row, internet freedom declined in the United States. The spread of conspiracy theories and manipulated content about the November 2020 elections threatened the core of American democracy, culminating in outgoing president Donald Trump's incitement of a violent attack on the US Capitol in a bid to halt certification of the election results on January 6, 2021. While the internet in the United States remains vibrant, diverse, and largely free from state censorship, government authorities in multiple cases responded to nationwide protests against racial injustice in 2020 with intrusive surveillance, harassment, and arrests. Separately, a number of new policies and proposed laws signaled a potential shift in approach by the new administration of President Joseph Biden, including his withdrawal of one Trump-era executive order aimed at reducing protections against intermediary liability and a pair of others that would have effectively banned the Chinese-owned platforms WeChat and TikTok.

The United States is a federal republic whose people benefit from a vibrant political system, a strong rule-of-law tradition, robust freedoms of expression and religious belief, and a wide array of other civil liberties. However, in recent years its democratic institutions have suffered erosion, as reflected in partisan pressure on the electoral process, bias and dysfunction in the criminal justice system, flawed and discriminatory policies on immigration and asylum seekers, and growing disparities in wealth, economic opportunity, and political influence.

(2) Violations of User Rights

Despite significant constitutional safeguards, laws such as the Computer Fraud and Abuse Act (CFAA) of 1986 have sometimes been used to prosecute online activity and impose harsh punishments. Certain states have criminal defamation laws in place, with penalties ranging from fines to imprisonment.

Instances of aggressive prosecution under the CFAA have fueled criticism of the law's scope and application. It prohibits accessing a computer without authorization, but fails to define the terms "access" or "without authorization," leaving the provision open to interpretation in the courts.

In one prominent case from 2011, programmer and internet activist Aaron Swartz secretly used Massachusetts Institute of Technology servers to download millions of files from JSTOR, a service providing academic articles. Prosecutors charged Swartz harshly under the CFAA, which could have resulted in up to 35 years' imprisonment. Swartz died by suicide in 2013 before his trial. After his death, lawmakers introduced "Aaron's Law," which would prevent the government from using the CFAA to prosecute terms-of-service violations and stop prosecutors from bringing multiple, redundant charges for a single crime. Until recently, reform efforts were largely unsuccessful. In April 2020, however, a court narrowed the scope of the CFAA by ruling in favor of researchers who were concerned that their work, which involved scraping data from websites, ran afoul of the law.

In June 2021, after the coverage period, the Supreme Court further limited the application of the CFAA and clarified the meaning of unauthorized access. The case, *Van Buren v. United States*, involved the conviction of a police officer who had accessed police databases for unofficial purposes. An amicus brief filed by several nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) argued for a narrow interpretation of the CFAA, asserting that a lower court's decision would have broadened the law's scope and turned it into "an all-purpose mechanism for policing objectionable or simply undesirable behavior."

All 50 states have laws that pertain to an array of illegal computer activities such as unauthorized access, hacking, denial of service attacks, and phishing.

Prosecutions or detentions for online activities are neither frequent nor systematic. However, the coverage period featured a number of cases in which people were arrested, charged, or threatened with criminal charges due to their actions online.

Internet users and online journalists have been investigated, arrested, and charged in connection with the protests against racial injustice that began in May 2020 and extended throughout the coverage period. The following were among the more widely reported cases:

- In June 2020, five people in New Jersey were charged with online harassment, a felony, for a Twitter post seeking to identify a masked police officer. One man was charged for publishing the post, while the other four had simply shared it.
- Also in June 2020, a *Cincinnati Enquirer* reporter was detained by police while covering protests after curfew, despite the fact that journalists qualified as essential workers and were exempt from the restriction.
- While reporting for Delaware Online the same month, journalist Jeff Neiburg was detained and forced onto a police bus for transportation out of the area surrounding Philadelphia's city hall.
- Journalist Gustavo Martínez Contreras was assaulted and arrested by police in June 2020 while live-streaming a George Floyd protest in Asbury Park, New Jersey. Charges were later dropped.
- In September 2020, social media journalist Chris Katami was arrested while reporting on racial justice protests in Portland, Oregon.

Smaller protests also led to the arrest of online journalists. As law enforcement officers in Los Angeles were attempting to clear out an encampment of people who are unhoused in March 2021, an estimated 13 reporters covering associated protests were detained, including representatives of the digital outlet LA Taco; independent photojournalist Ashley Balderrama, who was live-streaming the events on Instagram, was also among those detained. During

protests in response to the fatal police shooting of Black civilian Daunte Wright in Minnesota in April 2021, numerous journalists were arrested or detained, including Naasir Akailvi and Tracy Gunapalan of the social media news site the Neighborhood Reporter.

Some journalists were arrested while covering 2020 election-related protests and the subsequent attack on the Capitol. In November 2020, videographer Vishal Singh was arrested in Los Angeles while live-streaming such protests. Two *Washington Post* reporters working for the paper's live online news program were temporarily detained as they covered the unrest at the Capitol on January 6, 2021.

In January 2021, user Joshua Andrew Garton of Tennessee was detained for two weeks and charged with harassment for posting a doctored image on social media that depicted two police officers urinating on a gravestone. The charges were later dropped, and Garton sued local and state officials for violating his First Amendment rights.

Police have periodically detained or retaliated against individuals for using their mobile devices to upload images or stream live video of law enforcement activity; most face charges such as obstruction or resisting arrest. In 2017, federal courts upheld the right of bystanders to use their smartphones to record police actions.

At times, politicians have attempted to use legal cases to identify anonymous critics on the internet. In May 2021, Glenn Davis, a state lawmaker and candidate for lieutenant governor, filed a defamation lawsuit against the sender of a derogatory text message. Davis sought both to reveal the identity of the sender and to collect \$450,000 in damages. In March 2019, Representative Devin Nunes, a Republican from California, sued Twitter and the users of three anonymous accounts, alleging defamation and seeking \$250 million in damages; a Virginia judge overseeing the case ruled in June 2020 that Twitter was immune from liability under Section 230 of the Communications Decency Act, though the individual users were not protected by this ruling. The *New York Times* revealed in May 2021 that the DOJ under President Trump had issued a subpoena to Twitter in a bid to identify the user behind one of the anonymous accounts.

In January 2021, the DOJ charged Douglass Mackey, a far-right social media figure, with election interference after he mounted a disinformation and voter-suppression campaign during the 2016 election period. A lawyer at the National Association for the Advancement of Colored People (NAACP) Legal Defense Fund stated that the case could be the first in which the DOJ has brought criminal charges under civil rights laws for sharing election disinformation over social media.

The legal framework for government surveillance in the United States is open to abuse, and authorities have engaged in certain forms of monitoring, particularly on social media, with minimal oversight or transparency.

Federal, state, and local law enforcement bodies have access to a range of tools to monitor social media platforms and share the information they collect with other agencies; such monitoring is often directed at those involved in protests, at times justified by authorities as necessary to prevent or investigate violence. During the nationwide demonstrations against racial injustice in 2020, DHS and other agencies reportedly accessed and analyzed demonstrators' private communications through processes that appeared to lack judicial oversight (see B8). The Drug Enforcement Administration (DEA) gained new permission in June

2020 to “conduct covert surveillance” on protesters. In July 2020, the Intercept reported that certain police agencies received intelligence packages filled with content and data pulled from Twitter by the private company Dataminr. Reports have also confirmed that federal agencies or local police departments across the country, including in Pittsburgh, Minneapolis, Los Angeles, and Washington, DC, monitored and collected information from posts, comments, live streams, images, and videos that were shared on Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and other platforms.

In November 2020, the Intercept reported that the Austin Regional Intelligence Center, a law enforcement fusion center in Texas, surveilled not only protests on social media but also social gatherings and Black cultural events, including an online Juneteenth celebration. The center then developed documents that included organizers’ names or social media information, notable guests, and attendance totals, which were shared with other local, state, and federal law enforcement bodies. In September 2021, the Brennan Center for Justice revealed, via a public records request, that Los Angeles Police Department officers were authorized to collect social media information from any civilian they interviewed.

In April 2021, Yahoo News reported that the US Postal Service was operating an Internet Covert Operations Program that monitored social media for “inflammatory” content and then shared information across agencies. For example, the program monitored Telegram, Parler, Facebook, and other sites ahead of the World Wide Rally for Freedom and Democracy—meant to protest COVID-19 prevention measures—in March 2021. Following the attack on the Capitol on January 6, the DHS announced a new strategy to analyze social media to assess security threats.

In May 2019, the Department of State enacted a new policy that vastly expanded its collection of social media information. It required people applying for a US visa, about 15 million each year, to provide social media details, email addresses, and phone numbers going back five years. By the end of the coverage period, the Biden administration had not reversed the policy, though it had initiated a review. The administration indicated in May 2021 that it would defend the requirement in response to a lawsuit filed by the Brennan Center, the Knight First Amendment Institute at Columbia University, and the law firm Simpson Thacher & Bartlett LLP on behalf of two nonprofit documentary filmmaker organizations. However, in April 2021, the White House’s Office of Information and Regulatory Affairs rejected a DHS request to further expand its social media monitoring of people entering the country, arguing that the department had not proved the information to be helpful.

The government’s search and seizure powers are generally limited by the constitution’s Fourth Amendment, but federal authorities claim to have much greater leeway to conduct searches without a warrant within “border zones”—defined as up to 100 miles from any border, an area encompassing about 200 million residents. During the 2020 fiscal year, US Customs and Border Protection (CBP) reported 32,038 electronic device searches. By the end of March 2021, CBP reported 17,855 device searches, a 21 percent decrease from the same period a year earlier, which may be due to COVID-19 travel restrictions. The 2018 Directive No. 3340-049a provides CBP with broad powers to conduct device searches and requires travelers to provide their device passwords to CBP agents. CBP is known to have technology from the Israeli company Cellebrite that allows agents to extract information stored on a device or online within seconds. This information can then be stored in interagency databases that aggregate data from other monitoring programs.

Courts remain split on the legality of warrantless device searches at the border. In February 2021, a federal appellate court in Boston found the practice constitutional, reversing a 2019 district court decision that reasonable suspicion was necessary to justify a search. In June 2021, the Supreme Court denied a petition from the American Civil Liberties Union and the Electronic Frontier Foundation to review the appeals court's decision. A federal appeals court in San Francisco had significantly narrowed CBP's ability to conduct warrantless searches in 2019, limiting it to cases that relate to digital contraband, but the ruling is only binding within that court's jurisdiction, which includes California and eight other states.

In January 2021, an immigration lawyer in Texas reported that CBP had confiscated and searched his phone without a warrant when he returned from a trip abroad. The *Financial Times* reported in September 2020 that several Chinese students were pressured to hand over their electronic devices to CBP agents when leaving the United States.

The legal framework for foreign intelligence surveillance has in practice permitted the collection of data on US citizens and residents. Such surveillance is governed in part by the USA PATRIOT Act, which was passed following the terrorist attacks of September 11, 2001, and expanded official surveillance and investigative powers. In 2015, then president Obama signed the USA FREEDOM Act, which extended expiring provisions of the PATRIOT Act, including broad authority for intelligence officials to obtain warrants for roving wiretaps of unnamed "John Doe" targets and surveillance of lone individuals with no evident connection to terrorist groups or foreign powers. At the same time, the new legislation was meant to end the government's bulk collection of domestic call detail records (CDRs)—the metadata associated with telephone interactions—under Section 215 of the 2001 law. The bulk collection program, detailed in documents leaked by Edward Snowden in 2013, was ruled illegal by the US Second Circuit Court of Appeals in 2015.

The USA FREEDOM Act replaced the domestic bulk collection program with a system that allows the NSA to access US call records held by phone companies after obtaining an order from the Foreign Intelligence Surveillance Court, also called the FISA Court in reference to the 1978 Foreign Intelligence Surveillance Act. Requests for such access require use of a "specific selection term" (SST) representing an "individual, account, or personal device," a mechanism intended to prevent broad requests for records based on a zip code or other imprecise indicators. The definitions of SSTs vary, however, depending on the authority used, and civil liberties advocates have criticized them as excessively broad.

Another component of the USA FREEDOM Act established a panel of amici curiae with expertise in "privacy and civil liberties, intelligence collection, communications technology, or any other area that may lend legal or technical expertise" to the FISA Court, so that the judges are not forced to rely on the arguments of the government alone in weighing requests. The court must appoint an amicus in any case that "presents a novel or significant interpretation of the law." However, the court can waive this requirement by issuing "a finding that such appointment is not appropriate." Five people are currently designated to serve as amici curiae. In April 2021, the American Civil Liberties Union and several other parties petitioned the Supreme Court to evaluate whether the public has the right to know about the workings of the FISA Court.

Although reforms to Section 215 of the PATRIOT Act were supposed to end bulk collection of CDRs, official statistics showed that a massive number were still being acquired. In April 2019, the NSA recommended that the White House not seek reauthorization of the program because its operational complexities and legal liabilities outweighed the value of the intelligence gained.

The Trump administration nevertheless asked Congress to permanently reauthorize the CDR program, even as government watchdogs maintained that the CDR program authority was “highly invasive,” lacked evidence of efficacy in protecting the country from security threats, and was technically dysfunctional.

Section 215 ultimately expired in March 2020, after the Senate declined to take up a House-passed reauthorization bill. However, a “savings clause” allowed officials to continue using the authority for investigations that had begun before the expiration, or for new examinations of incidents that occurred before that date.

The Senate passed the draft USA FREEDOM Reauthorization Act in May 2020, with an amendment to strengthen the role of amici curiae by giving them greater access to information, granting them new authority to bring matters to the FISA Court, and adding to the categories of cases in which there should be a presumption that amici curiae will participate. The House, however, canceled a floor vote on the Senate-passed bill, and no further developments occurred during the coverage period.

Other components of the US legal framework allow surveillance by intelligence agencies, but often without adequate oversight, specificity, and transparency. Section 702, adopted in 2008 as part of the FISA Amendments Act, authorizes the NSA, acting inside the United States, to collect the communications of any foreigner overseas as long as a significant purpose of the collection is to obtain “foreign intelligence,” a term broadly defined to include any information that “relates to ... the conduct of the foreign affairs of the United States.” Section 702 surveillance involves both “downstream” (also known as PRISM) collection, in which stored communications data—including content—is obtained from US technology companies, and “upstream” collection, in which the NSA collects users’ communications as they are in transit over the internet backbone. Although Section 702 only authorizes the collection of information pertaining to foreign citizens outside the United States, Americans’ communications are inevitably swept up in this process in large amounts, and these too are stored in a searchable database.

In 2016, the government notified a FISA Court judge of widespread violations of protocols intended to limit NSA analysts’ access to Americans’ communications. The report showed that analysts had failed to take steps to ensure that they were not improperly searching the upstream database when conducting certain types of queries. In response, the court delayed reauthorizing the program, and in 2017 the NSA director recommended that the agency halt its collection of communications if they merely mentioned information relating to a surveillance target (referred to as “about” collection), and instead only collect communications to and from the target.

Section 702 was reauthorized for six years in January 2018 with few changes. The renewal legislation did not prohibit “about” collection, meaning the NSA could legally attempt to resume the practice as long as it obtained the FISA Court’s approval and gave Congress advance notice. The final bill did contain a narrow provision requiring a warrant when FBI agents seek to review the content of communications belonging to an American who is already the subject of a criminal investigation. The reauthorization also included measures to increase transparency, such as requiring that the attorney general brief members of Congress on how the government uses information collected under Section 702 in official proceedings such as criminal prosecutions.

In October 2019, the FISA Court released three opinions in which it found that tens of thousands of Americans had been subject to improper searches by the FBI. The court also determined that the FBI had violated the law by not reporting the number of times it conducted “US person queries.”

In April 2021, the intelligence community released its annual Statistical Transparency Report, which details the frequency with which the government uses certain national security powers. The number of Section 702 surveillance targets declined slightly from 204,968 in 2019 to 202,723 in 2020. The 2020 Statistical Transparency Report contained evidence of six instances in 2018 in which the FBI reviewed the contents of Americans’ communications after conducting a search in a criminal, non–national security case, but failed to obtain a warrant as required by law.

Under Title I of FISA, the DOJ may obtain a court order to conduct surveillance of Americans or foreigners inside the United States if it can show probable cause to suspect that the target is a foreign power or an agent of a foreign power. In March 2020, the department’s inspector general released a memorandum documenting pervasive errors in previous FISA applications, along with a failure to abide by internal procedures meant to ensure their accuracy.

Originally issued in 1981, Executive Order (EO) 12333 is the primary authority under which US intelligence agencies gather foreign intelligence; essentially, it governs all collection that is not governed by FISA, and it includes most collection that takes place overseas. The extent of current NSA practices that are authorized under EO 12333 is unclear and potentially overlaps with other surveillance authorizations. Although EO 12333 cannot be used to target a “particular, known” US person, the very fact that bulk collection is permissible under the order ensures that Americans’ communications will be incidentally collected, and likely in very significant numbers. Moreover, questions linger as to whether the government relies on EO 12333 to conduct any surveillance inside the United States that would not be subject to judicial oversight.

In criminal probes, law enforcement authorities can monitor the content of internet communications in real time only if they have obtained an order issued by a judge, under a standard that is somewhat higher than the one established under the constitution for searches of physical places. The order must reflect a finding that there is probable cause to believe a crime has been, is being, or is about to be committed.

Access to metadata for law enforcement, as opposed to intelligence, generally requires a subpoena issued by a prosecutor or investigator without judicial approval. Judicial warrants are only required in California, whose California Electronic Communications Privacy Act (CalECPA) has often been described as one of the nation’s best privacy laws since going into effect in 2016.

According to one ruling in federal court, the government must obtain a judicial warrant to access stored communications. However, the 1986 Electronic Communications Privacy Act (ECPA) states that the government can obtain access to email or other documents stored in the cloud with a subpoena, subject to certain conditions. Legislative attempts to further protect the privacy of email or other digital communications remain unproductive to date. In December 2020, a bipartisan group of lawmakers reintroduced the Email Privacy Act, which would require law enforcement bodies to show probable cause in court before accessing a person’s email.

Several government agencies have purchased extraction technology, including the DHS. An October 2020 report from the nonprofit UpTurn revealed that more than 2,000 state and local law enforcement agencies had the technology. School districts in Texas and California also reportedly have access to Cellebrite and other mobile-device forensic tools, which have been used on students' phones.

Several law enforcement agencies have access to cell-site simulators or IMSI (international mobile device subscriber identity) catchers—commonly known as “stingrays” after a prominent brand name—that mimic mobile network towers and cause nearby phones to send identifying information; the technology enables police to track targeted phones or determine the phone numbers of people in a given area. In a 2016 decision, a Maryland court rejected the argument that individuals using mobile phones are effectively “volunteering” their private information for use by third parties. Several courts have affirmed that police must obtain a warrant before using stingray technology. As of November 2018, the American Civil Liberties Union had identified 75 agencies across the country that use stingrays. In May 2020, the organization revealed that between 2017 and 2019, US Immigration and Customs Enforcement (ICE) had used stingray or similar devices at least 466 times. In November 2020, the California activist group Oakland Privacy won a lawsuit against the City of Vallejo and forced it to hold public hearings on a recently approved measure to purchase the devices. These hearings resulted in several privacy-enhancing changes, including new oversight mechanisms and limits on the monitoring of First Amendment–related activities and the sharing of data with immigration authorities.

Cyberattacks pose an ongoing threat to the security of networks and databases in the United States. Civil society groups, journalists, and politicians have also been subjected to targeted technical attacks.

Foreign actors have launched cyberattacks aimed at US infrastructure. In one of the largest and most sophisticated attacks in recent years, SolarWinds, a prominent information technology company, was compromised by an extensive infiltration attributed to the Russian government; it was first reported publicly in December 2020. The attackers used SolarWinds as a vehicle to penetrate federal government agencies, private-sector networks, think tanks, and civil society organizations, as the company's software updates were installed by more than 18,000 users. The Biden administration responded with sanctions against the Russian government in April 2021. In May 2021, hackers suspected of affiliation with the Russian-backed group Darkside carried out a ransomware attack on the Colonial Pipeline, one of the country's largest conduits for gasoline supplies, disrupting fuel delivery to significant portions of the East Coast. In response, President Biden issued an executive order designed to bolster federal cybersecurity networks. Also in May, the *New York Times* reported that a Russian intelligence service had hacked the US Agency for International Development's email systems.

Ahead of the US general elections in November 2020, Microsoft announced in September that a hacking unit associated with Russian military intelligence had targeted at least 200 organizations, including national and state political parties and political consultants. Iranian and Chinese hackers also targeted people associated with Trump's and Biden's presidential campaigns.

In December 2020, the US Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency and the FBI warned US think tanks whose work focused on national security and international affairs that state-sponsored hacking groups were seeking to break into their systems. Separately, in March

2021, the federal government revealed information about a cyberattack affecting more than 30,000 public and private entities that was later attributed to the Chinese government.

In June 2020, the Toronto-based research center Citizen Lab revealed that Dark Basin, a hack-for-hire group, had used phishing and other attacks against US NGOs working on issues related to net neutrality and a climate-change campaign called #ExxonKnew. Several journalists from major news outlets similarly faced technical attacks emanating from the group. From late May 2020, after the police killing of George Floyd, through the beginning of June, cyberattacks against advocacy groups increased by 1,120 times, including distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks against projects meant to raise bail funds for jailed protesters.

Cyberattacks against state and local governments are increasingly common. According to one analysis, between 2017 and August 2020, cyberattacks on state, local, tribal, and territorial governments rose by an average of nearly 50 percent. In a March 2021 report, the nonprofit K12 Security Information Exchange concluded that 2020 was a “record-breaking” year for technical attacks on education systems.

State and federal governments have launched a series of legal and policy initiatives to address the growing threat of cyberattacks. In May 2020, the Senate Commerce Committee approved the Cybersecurity Competitions to Yield Better Efforts to Research the Latest Exceptionally Advanced Problems (CYBER LEAP) Act of 2020. The legislation would establish incentives to develop innovative practices and technology related to the economics of cyberattacks, cyber training, and federal agency resilience to cyberattacks. At the end of the coverage period, the draft measure had not yet been reintroduced in the 2021–22 Congress. In 2020, at least 20 states passed cybersecurity bills, including provisions that increased penalties for cybercrimes, created advisory bodies to provide expert guidance on security issues, and offered support for training and education programs.

Conclusion

This Case Study, highlighting the precedent set by the Budapest Convention in consideration with countries which fall under ambit of the aforementioned jurisprudence, scenarios and general principals of its judicial law while including exceptions of ratification and withdrawal, paints a clear picture that under the actions and atrocities committed by state actors responsible for expediting the process and committing such acts (falling under all cases in Part 2) on the basis of cyber-attacks, cyber bullying hacking, financial frauds etc., it is advisable to initiate and strategize the appropriate mandates under the European Council and its relevant bodies to make such actors appear in trial for their actions in the under the unanimous decision under an advisory body and/or United Nations Human Rights Council